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Metadata for the *urbisphere*-Berlin campaign during 2021-2022: Technical Documentation

v1.0.0

2024-03-22

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Recommended citation:

Fenner, D., Christen, A., Gertsen, C., Grimmond, S., König, K., Looschelders, D., Meier, F., Metzger, S., Mitraka, Z., Morrison, W., Tsirantonakis, D. and Zeeman, M. (2024): Metadata for the *urbisphere*-Berlin campaign during 2021-2022: technical documentation, version v1.0.0.

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Acknowledgements

We are thankful to those who supported to create this report, namely Jörn Birkmann, Josefine Brückmann, Nektarios Chrysoulakis, Maria Gkolemi, Lars Mathes, and Timothy Sung.

Funding

The campaign was funded by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 855005). Some personnel and infrastructure were funded under grants UKRI NERC AMOF_20220419111152, UKRI EP/V010166/1, and UKRI NE/W002965/1, and by the Universities of Freiburg, Reading, Stuttgart, and Technische Universität Berlin.

Partner contributions

Beside the campaign activities by *urbisphere* (University of Freiburg – UFR, University of Reading – UR, FORTH Remote Sensing Lab – FORTH), a multitude of observations, many of which are long-term, were carried out by other institutions who provided access to data, instruments, as well as sites. These institutions were: (i) Technische Universität Berlin, Chair of Climatology (TUB), (ii) German Weather Service (DWD), (iii) Freie Universität Berlin, Department of Meteorology, (iv) Brandenburg University of Technology, Chair of Atmospheric processes (BTU), (v) HTW Berlin – University of Applied Sciences, Renewable Energy Systems, (vi) Landesbetrieb Forst Brandenburg (LFB), and (vii) Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT).

1 Scope and campaign design

1.1 Scope and motivation

The *urbisphere*-Berlin campaign aimed at investigating how the city of Berlin, Germany, modifies characteristics of the atmospheric boundary layer (BL) on diurnal to annual time scales, and at neighbourhood, i.e., intra-urban (local/sub-meso, $10^2 - 10^3$ m) to regional (meso, $10^1 - 10^2$ km) spatial scales. For the latter a focus was on the investigation of upwind and downwind rural regions of the city, thus, how BL characteristics are modified as air travels from upwind rural, over city, to downwind rural regions and forms an urban plume. With the aim to gain a deeper understanding of the interactions between the city and the BL, i.e., surface-BL coupling, a wide range of instruments for BL observations was deployed. These complement the extensive existing observations by partners and other institutions in the region. Overall, the goal was to create a spatially dense, city-specific data set of BL observations that allow a diverse range of investigations, from detailed process studies, over seasonal to annual investigations to be put into context of long-term studies, to in-depth model evaluation and further model development.

urbisphere-Berlin was the first of multiple campaigns within the European Research Council grant *urbisphere*, with the subsequent campaign carried out in Paris, France.

1.2 Campaign domain

The campaign encompassed the metropolitan region of Berlin, Germany, with the surrounding rural area (Figure 1). Three campaign rings were defined, surrounding the identified gravimetric city centre point (cf. Section 2 of the main article, Appendix A, Supplementary Material 1.1), describing inner city (A, radius 6 km), outer city (B, radius 18 km), and rural areas (C, radius 90 km).

Figure 1: Overview of campaign domain with land cover, including site locations and campaign rings (A, B, C)

1.3 Campaign period

The core campaign period was from 1 October 2021 to 30 September 2022. Some instruments were deployed already during summer 2021, most deployments ended in October 2022 (cf. Section 4.1). Long-term measurements by partner institutions go beyond this extended campaign period (cf. Table 2 of the main article).

Two intensive observation periods (IOP) were conducted in Spring (28/03-08/04/2022) and Summer (01/08-12/08/2022) of 2022. During the IOP, additional measurements were conducted on selected days, mainly radiosonde launches (Section 3.10), mobile ALC measurements (Section 3.11), and airborne observations (Section 3.12).

1.4 Weather conditions during the campaign

Overall, the campaign period was warmer than long-term climate conditions (1991-2020) by 1 K with a mean air temperature (T_{air}) of 11.4 °C compared to 10.4 °C (site TEMP, DWD 2022). Further, less precipitation ($PRCP$) was recorded during the campaign (440 mm) compared to the long-term mean value (570 mm).

Figure 2 summarises the weather conditions during the campaign period in comparison to the long-term climate. Regarding T_{air} , the months January, February, June and August 2022 were substantially warmer than typical climate conditions. $PRCP$ showed high variability along the months, with the months October 2021, January, March and Mai to July 2022 being particularly dry compared to the long-term climate conditions, while November 2021 and February 2022 were wetter (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Climate diagram with mean monthly air temperature (T_{air} , left y-axis) and monthly precipitation sum ($PRCP$, right y-axis) for the campaign period 10/2021-09/2022 (dark grey bars, solid lines, triangles) in comparison to the period 1991-2020 (light grey bars, dashed lines, points) at site TEMP. T_{max} : Daily maximum T_{air} (red), T_{mean} : Daily mean T_{air} (red), T_{min} : Daily minimum T_{air} (blue). Data source: DWD 2022.

Detailed weather conditions per day are given in Appendix A.1 Daily weather conditions.

Noteworthy are the following events:

- Two storms hit the Berlin region on 17 and 18 February 2022 with maximum recorded wind speed at TEMP being 25.9 and 27.9 m s⁻¹, respectively.
- From end of February until beginning of April 2022 a regional drought occurred with only 1.3 mm of precipitation, in combination with large amounts of sunshine and clear-sky conditions, as well as night-time $T_{air} < 0$ °C.
- The months May-July 2022 were particularly dry (Figure 2, combined 48 % of Normal) and in combination with high T_{air} led to drought conditions in the region up until mid-August.
- Several hot episodes with daily maximum $T_{air} \geq 25$ °C occurred from June to August 2022, some of them extending for a couple of weeks. Particularly hot were two episodes in June and August with daily maximum $T_{air} \geq 30$ °C for five consecutive days.
- Two Saharan dust events occurred in the Berlin region, 17 March and 13-14 April 2022.

2 General conventions

The following conventions apply:

- **Time zone** of data collection, archiving, and reporting: Universal Time Coordinated (UTC), otherwise noted. Local time in Berlin is UTC+1 (31/10/2021-27/03/2022), daylight savings (UTC+2) during the rest of the time of the campaign. Data collection (and sensor settings) for most sensors were set to UTC, independent of daylight saving periods.
- **Geographic referencing**: All spatial coordinates refer to the WGS 84 ellipsoid, EPSG:4326.
- **Vertical referencing**: All vertical coordinates (altitude, offsets) refer to the DHHN2016 height, EPSG:7837.
- **Azimuth degrees**: All azimuth degrees refer to geographic north, not magnetic and are given as degrees from north according to a compass rose (clock-wise).
- **Site naming scheme**: All campaign measurement sites were labelled with a four-letter code, which refers to the neighbourhood (within Berlin) or town (rural). Those codes are used in the main article and this document. Data archiving uses a six-letter code, consisting of “BE” (city identifier), followed by the four-letter site code, e.g., BEWEST for site WEST (Westend) in Berlin. This scheme enables archiving consistent for all *urbisphere* campaigns and is used when multiple cities are investigated together.
- **Instrumentation settings and data acquisition**: Detailed instrumentation settings (Section 3) and deployment details per site (Section 4.1) are mostly given for instruments set up by *urbisphere*. However, partner sites and instruments are nonetheless shown on the maps and relevant details are provided (Section 3), as they are essential contributions to the whole campaign network.
- **Maintenance details**: All *urbisphere* sites underwent regular maintenance at 2-3 weekly intervals. Detailed digitalised maintenance logs in the form of a spreadsheet are given alongside this document (Fenner et al. 2024) and should be consulted when working with the measurement data.

3 Instrumentation and data

This section provides relevant information for the different instrument groups, including details on instrument models, setup during the campaign, and data capture.

Data transmission from the devices to a central server architecture was performed via mobile routers and GSM connection or wired Ethernet connection. Data collection from partner institutions followed different schemes.

3.1 Automatic lidars and ceilometers

Automatic lidars and ceilometers (ALC) provide information on aerosol backscatter (β_{att}), cloud-base height, cloud cover, and linear polarisation ratio (LDR), allowing aerosol-concentration derived mixed-layer height (MLH, Kotthaus et al. 2018) and aerosol shape to be determined. During *urbisphere*-Berlin, the majority of the measurement sites consisted of ALC devices for BL characterisation and identification of the MLH and clouds. In combination with the Doppler-wind lidars (DWL, Section 3.2) they formed the core of the campaign network.

3.1.1 Instrument models

Three types of ALC were used, which differ in terms of their hardware and settings (Table 1, Table 2, Figure 3).

Table 1: Automatic Lidar and Ceilometer models deployed with details on manufacturers, laser specifications, relevant variables, relevant sampling configurations, and sites. β_{att} : Attenuated backscatter, CBH: cloud-base height, CCF: cloud-cover fraction, LDR: Linear depolarisation ratio, N: Number of devices.

Model; Manuf.	Laser source	Wavelength (nm)	Repetition rate (kHz)	Beam divergence	Range (m)	Variables	Sampling	N	Sites
CL61; Vaisala Oyj, Finland	InGaAs diode	910.55	9.5	± 0.2 mrad $\times \pm 0.35$ mrad	15,400	β_{att} , CBH, CC, LDR	15 s, gates: 4.8 m	5	ALTL, GRGL, HELL, TEMP, WEDD
CL31; Vaisala Oyj, Finland	InGaAs diode	910 \pm 10	10	± 0.4 mrad $\times \pm 0.7$ mrad	7500	β_{att} , CBH, CC	15 s, gates: 10 m	7	GRKR, MARI, MAVI, PLAN, TEMP, REIC, WEIS, WEST
CHM15k; Lufft/OTT HydroMet, Germany	Nd:YAG diode	1064	5 – 7	<0.5 mrad	15,000	β_{att} , CBH, CC	15 s, gates: 15 m	14	ANGE, BARU, FICH, FOGR, GENT, KYRI, LIND, MANS, NEUR, POTS, TEMP, TUCC, WIES, WITT

3.1.2 Setup and operations

The network of ALCs was designed to make both urban-rural and intra-urban investigations regarding measured variables possible. The network design considered existing sites, pre-dominant wind direction, and intra-urban variability of urban form and function (cf. Section 2 and 3 main article). One primary transect of devices (in combination with DWL) ran from rural through urban to rural settings, combined with one perpendicular and two parallel secondary transects, forming also an intra-urban grid (cf. Figure 2 main article). With 13 existing ALC in the region, mainly in rural settings (Figure 3, Table 2), most additional ALC deployments during the campaign were within Berlin.

ALC devices were positioned on the ground where possible and placed on roof tops for a more secure deployment at certain locations. CL31 were set up slightly tilted northwards, putting two M8 nuts underneath the southern side of the metal base plate.

Data capture and storage was on-device (CL61, CHM15k) or using a RaspberryPi with external solid state disk (CL61, CL31).

Regular on-site maintenance of ALCs consisted of checking if the window blower was working and cleaning the window.

Figure 3: Automatic Lidar and Ceilometer measurement sites with instrument models.

3.1.3 Hard- and software specifications

Table 2 provides details of all deployed ALC devices, including device-specific issues.

Table 2: Automatic Lidar and Ceilometer devices with hard- and software details and device-specific issues. Operators: DWD – Deutscher Wetterdienst/German Weather Service; FUB – Freie Universität Berlin; TUB – Technische Universität Berlin; UFR – University of Freiburg; * indicates long-term deployment beyond campaign period.

Model	Serial number	Site code	Operator	Hardware generation	Firmware version	Known issues
CL61	T2920393	TEMP, MOBI	UFR	611	v1.0, ≥11/04/2022: v1.1.6, ≥30/06/2022: v1.1.10	2022-04-11: Transmitter laser power alarm -> laser transmitter exchanged at manufacturer
	T2950755	ALTL, GRGL	UFR	611	v1.0, ≥08/06/2022: v1.1.6, ≥07/07/2022: v1.1.10	
	T3120614	HELL	UFR	611	v1.0, ≥08/06/2022: v1.1.6, ≥06/07/2022: v1.1.10	
	T3250605	GRGL, MOBI	UFR	611	v1.0, ≥05/07/2022: v1.1.10	2022-07-05: Transmitter laser power alarm (47 %)

						-> laser transmitter exchanged at manufacturer
	T3320613	WEDD	UFR	611	v1.0, ≥30/06/2022: v1.1.10	
CL31	B20202	GRKR	UFR	321, except: CLR311, CLO311	v3.0	2021-11-16: Detected window blower failure, installed new blower. Repeating pattern / “ringing” above thick clouds. Fall 2021: Condensation inside enclosure, desiccant places inside, solved issue.
	F2730001	WEST	UFR	321	v3.0	2021-12-19: Detected window blower failure; 2021-12-22: Installed new blower
	S2010715	REIC	UFR	321	v3.0	
	S2010716	PLAN	UFR	321	v3.0	
	S2010717	WEIS	UFR	321	v3.0	
	S2010718	MARI	UFR	321	v3.0	
	S2010719	TEMP, MAVI	UFR	321	v3.0	
CHM15k	CHM170115	ANGE*	DWD		17.05.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥19/07/2022: 17.05.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM160133	BARU*	DWD		15.06.1 2.13 1.040 1	
	CHM150150	FICH*	FUB		15.06.1 2.13 0.754 0	
	CHM160144	FOGR*	TUB		15.12.1 2.13 1.040 0	
	CHM180108	GENT*	FUB		17.05.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥18/07/2022: 17.05.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM070037	KYRI*	DWD		12.12.1 2.13 1.040 1	
	CHM190152	KYRI*	DWD		17.05.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM100110	LIND*	DWD		12.12.1 2.13 1.090 1, ≥19/07/2022: 12.12.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM160135	MANS*	DWD		15.06.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥22/07/2022: 15.06.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM180109	NEUR*	DWD		17.05.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥18/07/2022: 17.05.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM150113	POTS*	DWD		12.12.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥20/07/2022: 12.12.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM200117	TEMP*	DWD		18.10.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥28/09/2022: 18.10.1 2.13 1.110 1	
	CHM160145	TUCC*	TUB		15.12.1 2.13 1.040 0	
	CHM180127	WIES*	DWD		17.05.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥15/07/2022: 17.05.1 2.13 1.110 1	
CHM070042	WITT*	DWD		12.12.1 2.13 1.040 1, ≥13/07/2022: 12.12.1 2.13 1.110 1		

3.2 Doppler-wind lidars

In addition to the ALC, DWL can scan a variety of patterns and measure, in addition with β_{att} , the Doppler shift in the laser signal. These allow further variables to be derived from the measurements, most notably vertical wind speed and vertical profiles of wind speed and direction, as well as turbulence characteristics, and turbulence-derived mixing height (MH, Kotthaus et al. 2018). Combined with the ALC network (Section 3.1), the DWL formed the core of the campaign network.

3.2.1 Instrument models

Two instrument models were deployed during the campaign (Table 3), which differ mainly in terms of the maximum range (not relevant during the campaign) and the optical focus.

Table 3: Doppler-Wind Lidar models deployed with details on manufacturer, laser specifications, relevant variables, relevant instrument configurations, and sites. β_{att} : Attenuated backscatter, SNR: Signal-to-noise ratio, w : vertical velocity, WD: wind direction, WS: wind speed, N : Number of devices. + device-specific focus settings are given in Section 4.1 for each deployment.

Model; Manuf.	Wavelength (μm)	Pulse rate (kHz)	Variables	Optical focus ⁺	Gate width (m)	Number of gates	N	Sites
StreamLine; Halo Photonics/ Lumibird, France	1.5	10	β_{att} , SNR, w , WD, WS	adjustable	18, 30 (LIND)	200, 100 (LIND)	4	FRIE, LICH, LIND, SCHO
StreamLine XR; Halo Photonics/ Lumibird, France	1.5	10	β_{att} , SNR, w , WD, WS	None/infinity	18	200	2	TUCC, WILM

3.2.2 Setup and operations

During the campaign, three DWL were placed along the main transect in the inner-city region (sites WILM, FRIE, LICH, Figure 4) to complete the ALC network/main transect (cf. Section 3.1.2). Sites SCHO and TUCC were set up to also scan building wakes from high-building clusters near the Berlin Zoo area. DWL at LIND provides measurements in a rural setting.

The deployed DWL devices stored measurement data directly on the device.

DWL devices at urban locations were positioned mostly on roof tops, except one site (LICH).

Regular on-site maintenance of DWLs consisted of cleaning the lidar head window if visibly dirty, checking desiccant status and replacing if needed, checking if fans are clean and working, and checking instrument pitch and roll and adjusting if necessary.

Figure 4: Doppler-Wind Lidar measurement sites with instrument models.

During most of the campaign, all devices were set up with the following scan patterns. Further deployment-specific details are given in Section 4.1. The different scan patterns are:

- On the main transect (WILM, FRIE, LICH, Figure 4) and at TUCC until 28/07/2022: Every 5 minutes a 12-point velocity azimuth display (VAD) scan at 75° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray, duration approximately 54 s.
- On the main transect (WILM, FRIE, LICH, Figure 4) and at TUCC until 28/07/2022: Every 10 minutes a 6-point wind profile scan (VAD-6) at 75° elevation angle for operational purposes (live data previews), duration approximately 27 s.
- On the main transect (WILM, FRIE, LICH, Figure 4) from 28/07/2022: VAD scans were modified to 50,000 pulses/ray to reach higher altitudes. In addition to the 5-minute VAD scans, RHI (Range Height Indicator) scans were set up every 60 minutes along the main transect (250° azimuth angle, -2° to 182° elevation angle) and perpendicular to it (160° azimuth angle, -2° to 182° elevation angle).
- Remainder of the time: “Stare” scan undertaken measuring at 90° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray.
- At LIND: Continuous scan mode (~ 3.4 s) at 62° elevation angle with 3,000 pulses/ray, focus at 500 m
- At TUCC from 28/06/2022: Every 30 minutes a VAD-12 scan at 75° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray, duration approximately 54 s, every 10 minutes a VAD-6 wind-profile scan at 75° elevation angle for operational purposes (live data previews), duration approximately 27 s, and every 25 minutes a

PPI (Plan Position Indicator) scan at 0° elevation angle through azimuth angles 96°-210° at 2° resolution. The remainder of the time “Stare” at 90° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray.

- At SCHO from 28/06/2022: Every 18 minutes a PPI scan at 0° elevation angle through azimuth angles 150°-310° at 2° resolution. The remainder of the time “Stare” at 90° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray.

At the end of the campaign in October 2022, all DWL were set up concurrently at ROTH for a comparison measurement. During that time, all devices did only Stare measurements at 90° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray. Optical focus settings for devices with serial numbers 175 and 204 were changed after several days each, from no focus (i.e. “Infinity”, to 2000 m, to 800 m.

3.2.3 Hard- and software specifications

Table 4 provides details of all deployed DWL devices, including device-specific issues.

Table 4: Doppler-wind lidar devices with hard- and software details and device-specific issues. Operators: DWD – Deutscher Wetterdienst/German Weather Service; TUB – Technische Universität Berlin; UFR – University of Freiburg; UoR – University of Reading; * indicates long-term deployment beyond campaign period.

Model	Serial number	Site code	Operator	Firmware version	Known issues
StreamLine	175	FRIE	UFR	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi	
	204	LICH	UFR	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi	Overheating during hot weather with device switching off
	177	LIND*	DWD		
	03	SCHO	UoR/UFR	StreamLine XR v14-8.vi	Device potentially has a negative offset/bias in vertical velocity values
StreamLine XR	149	TUCC*	TUB	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi	Device potentially has a positive offset/bias ($\sim 0.26 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) in vertical velocity values; Hard-disk failure/overheating at times with instrument switching off and not automatically restarting
	143	WILM	TUB	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi	

3.3 Turbulent energy flux towers

Surface energy balance (SEB) measurements were an important component of the campaign to understand energy exchanges between (urban) surfaces and the atmosphere and to relate those to other observed variables, e.g. MLH. For a comprehensive understanding, turbulent-flux measurements were combined with radiation measurements (cf. Section 3.5). Turbulent-flux measurements during the campaign were mainly done by partner institutions with mostly long-term observations, only one site was additionally installed (MITT, Figure 5). The key derived variables from the measurements are turbulent energy fluxes of sensible (Q_H) and latent heat (Q_E). Q_H was additionally measured using Large Aperture Scintillometers (LAS, Section 3.4.19).

3.3.1 Instrument models

A variety of instrument models were used for turbulent flux measurements (Table 5). All three urban sites used an integrated device (IRGASON, Campbell Scientific), while rural observations were carried out using separate gas analysers combined with 3-D sonic anemometers-thermometers as eddy-covariance (EC) systems.

Table 5: Eddy-covariance systems deployed with instrument models, details on manufacturers, relevant variables, sampling frequency, and sites. u : u wind component, v : v wind component, w : vertical velocity, T_{air} : air temperature, p : air pressure, H_2O : water vapour density, CO_2 : carbon dioxide density, N : Number of devices.

Model; Manuf.	Variables	Sampling frequency (Hz)	N	Sites
IRGASON; Campbell Scientific, USA	u , v , w , T_{air} , p , H_2O , CO_2	20	3	MITT, ROTH, TUCC
LI-7500; LI-COR, USA	H_2O , CO_2	10 (LIND), 20 (KIEN)	2	LIND, KIEN
LI-7500DS; LI-COR, USA	H_2O , CO_2	10	1	MUEN
USA-1; METEK, Germany	u , v , w , T_{air}	10	1	LIND
WindMaster Pro; GILL, UK	u , v , w , T_{air}	10	1	MUEN
R3-50; GILL, UK	u , v , w , T_{air}	20	1	KIEN

3.3.2 Setup and operations

Three urban and three rural EC systems were operated during the campaign. One urban location (TUCC) is centrally located on a 10 m mast on a rooftop at the main campus of Technische Universität Berlin with medium-to-high density built-up environments and a large inner-city park in the footprints of turbulent fluxes. A second site (ROTH) is located in more open built-up structures with large amounts of vegetation as a more typical suburban site, the EC system measuring at 40 m agl. TUCC and ROTH are part of the Urban Climate Observatory (UCO) Berlin (<https://uco.berlin/en>), operated by TUB. ROTH is an associated site of the Integrated Carbon Observation System ICOS (https://meta.icos-cp.eu/resources/stations/ES_DE-BeR). The third site (MITT) was additionally set up and operated by UFR on top of a tall high-rise building in the inner city, surrounded by compact to open midrise building blocks.

One rural site (LIND) is located on a tower at 50 m agl at the Lindenberg Meteorological Observatory - Richard Assmann Observatory (MOL-RAO), location Falkenberg, also part of ICOS (https://meta.icos-cp.eu/resources/stations/AS_LIN) and operated by DWD. LIND is situated in a rural area on grassland, about 60 km south-east of Berlin. It is surrounded by predominantly agricultural land and a small forest to the west. The second rural site (KIEN) is located north of Berlin in a pine forest, operated by LFB. EC measurements are taken above the tree canopy (approximately 26 m agl) in 31 m agl. The site is an associated ICOS site (https://meta.icos-cp.eu/resources/stations/ES_DE-Kie). The third rural (MUEN) was located on an orchard with cherry trees, measuring at 4 m agl above the tree canopy (~3 m height), operated by BTU.

Data capture and storage was done using on-site data loggers (cf. Section 4.1 with deployment details).

Figure 5: Surface energy balance flux measurement sites.

3.4 Large-aperture scintillometer paths

LAS were set up and operated to obtain measurements of Q_H for large source areas, covering entire city neighbourhoods at the scale of mesoscale numerical models. They complemented Q_H measurements done by EC systems (Section 3.3). LAS observations require a transmitter-receiver pair to be within line of sight, placed above the roughness sublayer. Except for the rural measurement path at LIND, all LAS paths were set up during the campaign.

3.4.1 Instrument models

Three instrument models were used for LAS measurements of Q_H (Table 6).

Table 6: Large Aperture Scintillometer systems deployed with instrument models, details on manufacturers, relevant variables, sampling frequency, and sites/paths. C_n^2 : Refractive index structure parameter, Q_H : turbulent sensible heat flux, N : Number of devices.

Model; Manuf.	Variables	Path lengths (m)	Sampling	N paths	Sites
BLS450; Scintec, Germany	C_n^2 , Q_H	2549, 2833, 3513	continuous (cf. pulse) mode, 1-min averages	3	CHAR, GROF, MITT, NEUK, WEDD, WILM
BLS900; Scintec, Germany	C_n^2 , Q_H , cross-wind	2549, 4800	continuous (cf. pulse) mode, 1-min averages	2	GROF, NEUK, LIND
BLS2000; Scintec, Germany	C_n^2 , Q_H , cross-wind	4123, 4993, 6380	continuous (cf. pulse) mode, 1-min averages	3	CHAR, FRIE, GROF, MITT, OSWE, WEDD

3.4.2 Setup and operations

The LAS transmitter-receiver pairs were installed on top of tall buildings in the city with different types of land use/land cover in the flux footprint areas (Figure 6). The rural path (LIND) is operated as a long-term deployment above cropland/grassland. Source-area analyses informed the final urban site locations to ensure measurements of all predominant urban form and function types, and to confirm that the integrated measurement heights were above the roughness sublayer.

The deployed LAS systems had system-specific data loggers, i.e., signal processing units, for on-site data capture and storage.

Regular on-site maintenance of LAS consisted of cleaning the transmitter and receiver window if visibly dirty and checking if all LED are working (transmitter only)

Figure 6: Large Aperture Scintillometer measurement paths and involved sites. Measurement path at LIND outside map extent.

3.4.3 Hard- and software specifications

Table 7 provides details of all deployed LAS devices, including device-specific issues. Several transmitters had faulty LED modules with failing LED over time. The number of LED segments malfunctioning at each maintenance event per site are given in the detailed maintenance table.

Table 7: Large Aperture Scintillometer devices with software details and device-specific issues. Operators: DWD – Deutscher Wetterdienst/German Weather Service; UFR – University of Freiburg; * indicates long-term deployment beyond campaign period.

Model	Transmitter serial number	Receiver serial number	SPU serial number	Path	Operator	SPU software version	Known issues
BLS450	T-E-1059	T-E-1053	T-E-1050	CHAR-WILM	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	
	T-E-1061	T-E-1055	T-E-1056	NEUK-GROP	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	Failing transmitter LED modules. 2022-03-31: LED module replaced, old with 2 LED off. 2022-05-19: Dismounted transmitter, 6 LED off and two with low intensity.
	T-E-1060	T-E-1054	T-E-1051	WEDD-MITT	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	Failing transmitter LED modules. 2022-01-21: LED module replaced, old with 6 LED off. 2022-03-31: LED module replaced, old with >10 LED off. 2022-05-23: Dismounted transmitter, 6 LED off. Until 2022-02-09: Receiver at MITT with potential vibration due to tall stand at high wind speeds.
BLS900	T-E-0609	T-E-1054	T-E-1051	NEUK-GROP	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.67	
BLS2000	T-E-1078	T-E-1074	T-E-1082	CHAR-MITT	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	Until 2022-02-09: Receiver at MITT with potential vibration due to tall stand at high wind speeds.
	T-E-1079	T-E-1077	T-E-1081	OSWE-GROP	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	2022-02-17: 1 LED off
	T-E-1078	T-E-1077	T-E-1081	OSWE-GROP	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	
	T-E-1075	T-E-1076	T-E-1083	WEDD-FRIE	UFR	SRun-Scin 1.66	Failing transmitter LED modules. 2021-12-15: 1 LED off. 2022-01-21: LED module replaced, old with 6 LED off.

3.5 Radiometer observations

Observations of radiation fluxes were crucial to obtain data and gain an understanding on the influence of the city on downwelling radiation fluxes (including urban-plume effects), as well as to complement turbulent-flux measurements (Section 3.3). A number of radiation flux measurements in the region are long-term observations by partner institutions. Many of those are measurements of all four components of the radiation balance, i.e., downwelling short- (K_{\downarrow}) and longwave (L_{\downarrow}) radiation fluxes as well as upwelling short- (K_{\uparrow}) and longwave (L_{\uparrow}). Additional instrumentation by *urbisphere* mainly focused on downwelling fluxes measured with Sun trackers, including measurements of K_{\downarrow} , L_{\downarrow} (shaded), diffuse shortwave radiation (D), and Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) perpendicular to the sun.

3.5.1 Instrument models

Different types of radiometers were used by the different institutions (Table 8).

Table 8: Device models for radiation flux measurements deployed with details on manufacturers, variables, relevant device details, and sites. DNI: Direct Normal Irradiance, D: Diffuse shortwave radiation, K_{\downarrow} : Downwelling shortwave radiation, L_{\downarrow} : Downwelling longwave radiation, K_{\uparrow} : Upwelling shortwave radiation, L_{\uparrow} : Upwelling longwave radiation N: Number of devices.

Model; Manuf.	Type	Variable(s)	Comment	N	Sites
CHP1, Kipp & Zonen	Pyrheliometer	DNI		4	FRIE, GROF, GRUN, MAVI
SHP1, Kipp & Zonen	Pyrheliometer	DNI		1	OSWE
SMP21, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	D	Shaded	1	OSWE
SPN1, DeltaT-Devices	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow} , D		2	ROTH, TUCC
CM11, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow}		1	POTS
CM21, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow} , D	Shaded instrument for D	5	FICH, FRIE, GROF, GRUN, MAVI
CM22, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow}		1	LIND
CMP11, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow}		1	OSWE
CMP22, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow}		1	OSWE
SMP21, Kipp & Zonen	Pyranometer	K_{\downarrow}		1	POTS
CG1, Kipp & Zonen	Pyrgeometer	L_{\downarrow}		4	FRIE, GROF, GRUN, MAVI
CGR4, Kipp & Zonen	Pyrgeometer	L_{\downarrow}		3	FRIE, LIND, POTS
CNR4, Kipp & Zonen	Net radiometer	K_{\downarrow} , L_{\downarrow} , K_{\uparrow} , L_{\uparrow}		3	KIEN, ROTH, TUCC
NR01, Hukseflux	Net radiometer	K_{\downarrow} , L_{\downarrow} , K_{\uparrow} , L_{\uparrow}		1	MUEN
SOLYS2, Kipp & Zonen	Sun tracker		Including sun sensor and GPS	4	FRIE, GROF, GRUN, MAVI
RaZON ⁺ , Kipp & Zonen	Sun tracker		Including GPS	1	OSWE

3.5.2 Setup and operations

While a number of long-term radiation flux measurement sites already existed in the study region, four additional radiometer sites with sun trackers were set up (Figure 7) in a cross-like pattern along and across the main transect (Figure 3 of the main article), centred on the inner-city site FRIE. Those observations were set up in order to study urban effects on downwelling radiation fluxes due to BL modifications by the city, including urban plume effects. Besides FRIE, sun trackers with high-quality radiometers were set up at GROF, GRUN, and MAVI at the southern, western, and northern boundary of the built-up area of Berlin, respectively. A fifth site in the NE of Berlin near site HELL was planned, yet could not be realised as no suitable location could be secured.

Radiometer at those locations were placed in custom-built aluminium housings with permanent ventilation and heating at near- and below-zero °C conditions. Housings were painted white and had a radiation shield on top.

Long-term urban observations are carried out by TUB (ROTH, TUCC), FUB (FRIE), and HTW (OSWE). Observations outside Berlin include long-term measurements by the DWD at LIND as a station in the Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN, station no. 12, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.669521>) and POTS, long-term observations by LFB at KIEN, and temporary measurements by BTU at MUEN. Radiation flux measurements at KIEN, LIND, MUEN, ROTH, and TUCC complement the turbulent energy flux measurements at those sites (Section 3.3).

Figure 7: Radiation flux measurement sites.

3.5.3 Hardware specifications

Table 9 lists all radiation flux instruments deployed, including relevant meta data.

Table 9: Radiation flux measurement devices with details on setups. Variables: DNI: Direct Normal Irradiance, D: Diffuse shortwave radiation, K_{\downarrow} : Downwelling shortwave radiation, L_{\downarrow} : Downwelling longwave radiation, K_{\uparrow} : Upwelling shortwave radiation, L_{\uparrow} : Upwelling longwave radiation. Operators: BTU: Brandenburg University of Technology, DWD – Deutscher Wetterdienst/German Weather Service, FUB: Freie Universität Berlin, HTW – HTW Berlin - University of Applied Sciences, LFB: Landesbetrieb Forst Brandenburg, TUB: Technische Universität Berlin. UFR – University of Freiburg; * indicates long-term deployment beyond campaign period.

Model	Serial number	Site code	Variable(s)	Operator	Ventilation	Heating	Last calibration	Comment
CHP1	190791	FRIE	DNI	UFR	No	No	12/12/2019	
	210927	GROP	DNI	UFR	No	No	25/11/2021	
	210924	GRUN	DNI	UFR	No	No	30/11/2021	Misaligned?
	210925	GRUN	DNI	UFR	No	No	25/11/2021	
	210926	MAVI	DNI	UFR	No	No	25/11/2021	
SHP1		OSWE*	DNI	HTW	No	No		
SMP21		OSWE*	D	HTW	No	No		Shaded (disk)
SPN1		ROTH*	K_{\downarrow} , D	TUB	No	No		
		TUCC*	K_{\downarrow} , D	TUB	No	No		

CM11		POTS*	K↓	DWD				
CM21	990643	FRIE	D	UFR	Permanent	Yes	15/10/2020	Shaded (ball), radiation shield
	940204	GROP	D	UFR	Permanent	Yes	15/10/2020	Shaded (ball), radiation shield
	990644	GRUN	D	UFR	Permanent	Yes	17/11/2020	Shaded (ball), radiation shield
	930104	MAVI	D	UFR	Permanent	Yes	15/10/2020	Shaded (ball), radiation shield
	940174	FICH*	D	FUB	No	No		Shaded (ring)
	020960	FICH*	K↓	FUB	No	No		
	990642	FRIE	K↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes	17/11/2020	Radiation shield
	990645	GROP	K↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes	15/10/2020	Radiation shield
	010867	GRUN	K↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes	15/10/2020	Radiation shield
	041181	MAVI	K↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes	15/10/2020	Radiation shield
CM22		LIND*	K↓	DWD				
CMP11		OSWE*	K↓	HTW				
CMP22		OSWE*	K↓	HTW				
SMP21		POTS*	K↓	DWD				
CG1	000206	FRIE, GROP	L↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes		Shaded (ball), radiation shield
	000203	GRUN	L↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes		Shaded (ball), radiation shield
	010238	MAVI	L↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes		Shaded (ball), radiation shield
CGR4	120530	FRIE	L↓	UFR	Permanent	Yes		Shaded (ball), radiation shield
		LIND*	L↓	DWD				
		POTS*	L↓	DWD				
CNR4		KIEN*	K↓, L↓, K↑, L↑	LFB	Permanent			
		ROTH*	K↓, L↓, K↑, L↑	TUB	Permanent			
		TUCC*	K↓, L↓, K↑, L↑	TUB	Permanent			
NR01		MUEN	K↓, L↓, K↑, L↑	BTU	No	Yes		
SOLYS2	200613	FRIE		UFR				Including sun sensor and GPS
	210712	GROP		UFR				Including sun sensor and GPS
	210708	GRUN		UFR				Including sun sensor and GPS
	210713	MAVI		UFR				Including sun sensor and GPS
RaZON ⁺		OSWE*		HTW				Including GPS

Data capture and storage was done using on-site data loggers (cf. Section 4.1 with deployment details).

Regular on-site maintenance of radiometers and sun trackers operated by UFR (FRIE, GROP, GRUN, MAVI) consisted of checking if all devices are level and adjusting if needed, if the ventilation unit is clean and running, cleaning the radiometer domes and radiation shields, checking if the alignments of the sun spot of the pyrliometer and the shading balls (sun tracker), and checking the desiccant status and replacing it if needed.

3.6 Sun photometer observations

Sun photometers provide optical properties crucial for estimating aerosol direct radiative forcing. The sun photometers deployed measure sun, sky, and lunar light to determine Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Volume Size Distribution, complex refractive index (n), shape factor, and water vapour content.

During *urbisphere*-Berlin, one additional sun photometer was deployed and operated at the inner-city site (FRIE), complementing long-term observations at FICH and LIND by partner institutions, namely FUB and DWD,

respectively. All sites are part of AERONET (AErosol RObotic NETwork), a global network dedicated to aerosol measurement.

3.6.1 Instrument models, setup, and operations

The three sun photometers (CE318-T, Cimel Electronique) were operated at FICH, FRIE, and LIND according to AERONET standards (https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/system_descriptions_operation.html). The CE318-T is a multi-wavelength automatic sun-sky-moon photometer, measuring direct solar irradiance and sky radiance at nine bands centred at 340 nm, 380 nm, 440 nm, 500 nm, 675 nm, 870 nm, 937 nm, 1020 nm, and 1640 nm (10 nm FWHM), with a field of view of 1.2°.

Data from the sun photometers is automatically uploaded to the AERONET server, where operational data quality control is performed. AERONET indicates an approximate AOD accuracy of 0.01-0.02 for field-operated sun photometers, with sky radiance measurements having a +/- 5% accuracy. Further details on accuracy assessment are available (http://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/system_descriptions_calibration.html).

Regular on-site maintenance of the sun photometer at FRIE consisted of checking if the device is level and for the correct sun spot position, adjusting if needed, and cleaning the collimator tubes if dirty (e.g. spider webs).

3.7 Surface infrared thermometry

Two types of instruments were deployed for measuring surface temperature (T_s), infrared thermometers (IRT) and thermal infrared (TIR) cameras. IRT sensors were installed at three locations to sample different types of predominant roof materials, while the TIR cameras at one site (GROP) were set up to derive complete T_s at one location.

3.7.1 Instrument models and setup

Table 10 provides an overview of the instruments deployed, including relevant sensor specifications.

Table 10: Instruments of surface infrared thermometry measurements. IRT: Infrared thermometer, TIR: Thermal-infrared.

Model; Manuf.	Type	Wavelength (μm)	Resolution	Sampling/Storage	N	Sites
IR120; Campbell Scientific, USA	IRT	8 - 14	1	10-seconds, averaged and logged at 1 minute	6	GROP, TEMP, TUCC
PI-160; Optris, Germany	TIR camera	7,5 - 14	160x120 pixels	60-seconds	4	GROP

IRT sensors (field of view: 20°, half angle) were installed at 0.5-1.5 m above surface level with two devices per site at GROP, TEMP, and TUCC, measuring felt, grass, and gravel surfaces, respectively.

TIR cameras installed at GROP (cf. Morrison et al. 2020 for further device specifics) allowed approximately 100 m² measurements of the surrounding buildings, roads, and vegetation from all cardinal directions at ~0.5 – 2 m spatial resolution (Figure 8). The cameras were set up in weather-proof housings with silver reflective coating with a shutter in front of the lenses that opened and closed just before and after image capture, respectively.

Figure 8: Surface temperature (T_s) as captured by thermal-infrared cameras installed at GROF on 03/08/2022 09:00 UTC with view directions of cameras indicated. Coordinates at axes refer to pixel number.

Data capture and storage of IRTs was on CR1000X and CR3000 data loggers (Campbell Scientific), of TIR cameras on RaspberryPis.

Regular on-site maintenance of IRTs consisted of cleaning the tubes and the sensor head if visibly dirty.

3.8 Phenocams

Phenocams are cameras that monitor patches of vegetation and are used in a variety of applications such as seasonal changes tracking, phenology modeling and EO data validation. Two cameras were deployed within Berlin for long-term monitoring. Both cameras were installed on existing towers after the main campaign period (Table 11).

3.8.1 Instrument models and setup

Two Stardot NetCam SC 5MP IR cameras (2592x1944 pixels) with RGB and infrared (IR) image capture were installed in weather-proof housings with wired Ethernet connection for data transfer (Table 11).

Table 11: Phenocam sites and relevant installation details.

Site code	Phenocam sitename	Type	Installation date	Height (m agl)	Azimuth angle (°)	Tilt angle (°)	Data access
ROTH	rothberurb	Urban/ Residential	06/11/2022	35	309	-15	https://phenocam.nau.edu/webcam/sites/rothberurb/
TUCC	tubberurb	Urban/ Commercial	01/06/2023	51	38	-15	https://phenocam.nau.edu/webcam/sites/tubberurb/

The cameras were set-up using the PhenoCam Network standards, using the open-source installation tool (https://github.com/bluegreen-labs/phenocam_installation_tool) to configure the camera settings and timing regarding image acquisitions and following the installation guide provided by the PhenoCam Network (https://phenocam.nau.edu/pdf/PhenoCam_Install_Instructions.pdf).

The cameras were programmed to capture images (RGB and RGB+NIR) at 30-minute intervals and instantly upload the images to the PhenoCam server via ftp. For both cameras the acquisition times was set to begin at 06:00 and stop at 23:00 local time (CET/UTC+1). The exact timings of the image acquisitions differ and are adjusted based on the incoming ftp traffic to the PhenoCam Network database. For both sites the timestamp of the data was set to CET (UTC+1). This does not change during the period of summer daylight saving.

At ROTH, a colored (RGB + white) reference panel was installed and is visible in the bottom left corner of the camera field of view (Figure 9 left), which can be used for image calibration during data analysis. Due to site-specific technical limitations, this could not be done at TUCC. However, the image metadata include the exact exposure settings of the camera during acquisition, so this does not hinder the usability of the acquired data.

The camera at ROTH overlooks a residential area between Schmidt-Ott Strasse and Grunewaldstrasse in the Steglitz area of Berlin, densely vegetated with dominant cover of broadleaf deciduous vegetation (Figure 9 left). The camera at TUCC overlooks a commercial area on the Straße des 17. Juni in the center of Berlin, with a few patches of tree canopies and several street trees present in the field of view (Figure 9 right).

Figure 9: Exemplary images of the fields of view of the Phenocams at ROTH (left) and TUCC (right). Black areas are privacy filters, which are set in the camera settings.

3.9 Automatic weather stations

A large number of long-term automatic weather stations (AWS) is operated by different institutions in the Berlin region, including measurements by the DWD (DWD 2023a, b), Technische Universität Berlin (Fenner et al. 2014, <https://uco.berlin/en/ucon>), and Freie Universität Berlin (Langer et al. 2021, <https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/met/service/wetterdaten/index.html>, <https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/en/met/ag/Stadtklima/FUMiNet-OpenStreetMap/index.html>). Detailed descriptions of sites and instruments can be found at the respective references and webpages. An overview of all sites and available data is provided by the UCO Berlin at <https://uco.berlin/en/dataportal>.

During *urbisphere*-Berlin, six additional AWS (ClimaVUE50, Campbell Scientific; CR1000X data logger, Campbell Scientific) were deployed at FRIE, GROP, GRUN, MAVI, WEST, and WEDD, alongside other measurements and mainly to support those other measurements. Those AWS provide measurements of T_{air} , RH , vapour pressure, air pressure, wind speed and direction, precipitation, global radiation, and lightning strikes. Measurement frequency was set to 10-seconds, averaged/summed to and stored as 1-minute means.

3.10 Radiosoundings

Radiosondes provide measurements of atmospheric conditions along their ascent from the ground into the atmosphere. During *urbisphere*-Berlin, radiosonde launches were carried out on selected days during the IOPs at selected sites to mainly support other measurements (e.g. atmospheric corrections of airborne/satellite-based remote sensing), to further investigate BL structure alongside, e.g. ALC measurements, and for numerical model evaluation. During two days (04/08/2022, 11/08/2022), concurrent launches at an inner-city and a rural site were carried out along the diurnal cycle every 2-3 hours to investigate urban-rural differences in BL structure.

3.10.1 Instrument model

Radiosonde data, in addition to operational radiosonde launches at LIND (<https://www.gruan.org/network/sites/lindenberg>), was gathered by the “Windsond” radiosonde system (Sparv Embedded AB, <http://windsond.com/>). Single-use (S1H3-S) and reusable (S1H3-R) Windsonds were used. Reusable Windsonds enable to cut the tethered cord by a hot wire at a pre-defined height or upon operator decision during the ascent.

The Windsond system consists of a Styrofoam enclosure (height: 8.8 cm, diameter: 4.5 cm (top), 7.4 cm (bottom), 13.9 g total weight), containing sensors for measurements of T_{air} , relative humidity (RH), and air pressure, a global positioning system (GPS), a battery, and a radio transceiver for data transmission (Figure 10). This measurement system was tethered with a 5 m long cord to latex balloons filled with helium (~123 cm circumference), enabling an ascent speed of approximately 2 m s^{-1} . A sonde can ascend up to >10 km above ground level (agl), depending on weather conditions and the amount of helium in the balloon.

Measurement data is continuously transmitted to a ground-based receiver during the ascent and during the drop of the sonde after balloon burst or cut-off. The receiver (models used: RR1- 250 and RR2) was connected to a laptop, on which data was stored using the Windsond software (v2.112). Measurement frequency was 1 Hz/every second (GPS data every three seconds).

Figure 10: Windsond S1H3-S/R radiosonde with relevant components indicated, (a) outside and (b) inside. (c) Radiosonde attached to a helium balloon during an ascent on 4 August 2022.

During the ascents, the following variables are recorded:

- Time (UTC)
- Altitude above mean sea level (m)
- Altitude above ground level (m)
- Air pressure (Pascal) ± 1 hPa accuracy, 0.02 hPa resolution
- Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), ± 0.2 K accuracy, 0.01 K resolution
- Relative humidity (%), ± 1.8 % accuracy, 0.05 % resolution
- Internal temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), ± 0.2 K accuracy, 0.01 K resolution
- (Wind) speed (m s^{-1}), 5 % accuracy, 0.1 m s^{-1} resolution
- Heading (degrees), accuracy dependent on GPS connection, 0.1° resolution
- Latitude (degrees)
- Longitude (degrees)
- Rise speed (m s^{-1})

3.10.2 Launches

An overview of radiosonde launch sites is presented in Figure 11, all Windsond launches are given in Table 12.

Figure 11: Radiosonde launch sites. Sites with multiple launches are labelled according to their site code, single launches by date in 2022 and time (UTC), cf. Table 12.

Table 12: Windsond launches conducted during urbisphere-Berlin, ordered by launch date-time, with relevant sonde and launch details, and prevailing weather conditions.

Date	Time (UTC)	Site/ Location (° N, °E)	Sonde ID	Balloon circumference (cm)	Weather conditions	Comments
28/03/2022	08:24	TEMP	7277	123	Wind from W	Along mobile measurement route
28/03/2022	10:45	52.498240, 13.679075	7246	123	Wind from W	Along mobile measurement route
28/03/2022	11:23	52.489435, 14.009774	7247	123	Wind from W	Along mobile measurement route
28/03/2022	14:07	TEMP	7268	123	Wind from W	Along mobile measurement route
29/03/2022	09:10	52.548318, 13.119602	7269	123	Wind from WNW	Along mobile measurement route
29/03/2022	10:07	52.511680, 13.351959	7278	123	Wind from WNW	Along mobile measurement route
29/03/2022	10:53	52.489239, 13.463599	7266	123	Wind from WNW	Along mobile measurement route
29/03/2022	11:48	52.402906, 13.750447	7265	123	Wind from WNW	Along mobile measurement route
30/03/2022	06:55	52.288867, 13.277220	7250	123	Wind from N	Along mobile measurement route
30/03/2022	08:52	TEMP	7251	123	Wind from N	Along mobile measurement route
01/08/2022	20:30	WEST	7274	123	Partly cloudy, slight wind from NW/N	Intermittent data connection >3500 m agl
02/08/2022	9:29	ROTH	7270	123	Sunny with very few clouds, light westerly winds	
02/08/2022	14:54	ROTH	7267	123	Sunny with high and thin Cirrus clouds, very low westerly winds	
04/08/2022	03:30	ROTH	7272	123	Clear with few Altocumulus	
04/08/2022	06:15	GLEI	8190	123	Clear skies, thin clouds on horizon	
04/08/2022	06:15	ZOSS	7247	123	Sunny, no clouds, slight winds from S	Potential sensor offset (T_{air} , RH)
04/08/2022	08:05	GLEI	8189	123	Mostly clear, some thin clouds, wind direction at surface: E	
04/08/2022	08:07	ZOSS	7251	123	Sunny, few thin Cirrus clouds	
04/08/2022	09:50	GLEI	8188		More clouds, slight breeze from SE	Potential sensor offset (RH)
04/08/2022	09:50	ZOSS	8195	123	Sunny, thin Cirrus clouds, wind speed increased from S	Potential sensor offset (T_{air})
04/08/2022	11:31	GLEI	7252	>123		Potential sensor offset (T_{air} , RH)
04/08/2022	11:32	ZOSS	8196	123	Sunny, thin but increasing clouds, higher wind speed from S	
04/08/2022	13:16	GLEI	8185	123		Balloon burst at 1500 m
04/08/2022	13:17	ZOSS	7250	123	Sunny, some BL and Cirrus clouds, moderate wind from S	Lost signal soon
04/08/2022	16:10	GLEI	8184	123	Partial cloud cover, wind from WSW	
04/08/2022	16:10	ZOSS	7248	130	Sunny, few BL clouds, moderate wind from SW	

04/08/2022	19:10	GLEI	8183	123	Almost clear sky, slight wind from WSW	Potential sensor offset (T_{air} , RH)
04/08/2022	19:10	ZOSS	7249	125	Clear, sunset, no clouds, calm	
04/08/2022	21:00	GLEI	7273	123	Slightly cloudy, wind from SE	
04/08/2022	21:00	ZOSS	7245	125	Clear, no clouds, calm	
10/08/2022	20:40	WEST	7271	123	Cloud free, calm, light breeze from N/NE	GPS signal intermittently lost starting 21:55
11/08/2022	04:18	ROTH	7246	125	Cloud-free, calm	Potential sensor offset (T_{air} , RH)
11/08/2022	06:15	RAGO	8182	130	Cloud-free, light wind from E	
11/08/2022	06:15	GLEI	8194	123	Cloud-free, medium wind from SE	
11/08/2022	08:00	GLEI	8194	130	Cloud-free, medium wind from SE	
11/08/2022	10:00	GLEI	8192	130	Cloud-free, medium wind from SE	
11/08/2022	10:32	RAGO	8181	130	Cirrus clouds, moderate wind from E	
11/08/2022	12:00	GLEI	8191	130	Cloud-free, medium wind from NW	
11/08/2022	14:00	GLEI	7244	130	Few BL and Cirrus clouds, light wind from E	

3.11 Mobile measurements

Mobile measurements were conducted to provide additional high spatio-temporal ALC data during selected days. Further, the mobile unit allowed to conduct comparison measurements of two ALC while deployed in the field to identify potential sensor faults (cf. Table 2). Measurements were mainly carried out during the two IOPs periods, combined with radiosonde launches (Section 3.10).

3.11.1 Measurement setup

To conduct mobile measurements with an ALC, we built a system that allows continuous measurements while driving, as well as temporary stationary deployments. Core of the system is a CL61 ALC (Vaisala) below an open skylight in a van (Figure 12). The ALC has the capabilities to monitor β_{att} and LDR, thus aerosol content and shape with a high signal-to-noise ratio. The ALC is fitted on a custom-built aluminium frame that holds the measurement and power unit of the ALC without the white radiation shield. The frame is mounted on a wooden base plate with six rubber shock absorbers, the base plate is secured in the van. Additionally, a HygroVUE10 probe (SN: E1722, Campbell Scientific) measures T_{air} and RH in a radiation shield mounted approximately 20 cm above the van roof (Figure 12 left). A GPS antenna (GPS16X-HVS, Garmin) provides geo-location, a cellular router with antenna enables internet access, time syncing of devices, and access to all devices via Ethernet connection by the operator. ALC data is stored on a RaspberryPi with SSD storage, data from the other sensors is captured by a CR1000X data logger (Campbell Scientific). Sensors and data loggers are powered from the car using an inverter and can easily be removed after deployments.

ALC data was sampled and stored at the highest possible resolution of 5 and 10 seconds for β_{att} and LDR, respectively. Other data (T_{air} , RH , location) were sampled and stored at 1 second resolution.

Figure 12: Mobile measurement unit with CL61 mounted on an aluminium frame below an open skylight and shielded air-temperature and relative humidity probe above the van roof (left), ALC below skylight with additional GPS and mobile phone antenna (right).

3.11.2 Measurement tours

An overview of all measurement tours is provided in Figure 13 with further details of the tours in Table 13.

Figure 13: Mobile measurement tours, coloured by day. Further tour details are given in Table 13. Note that routes might have been taken in both directions.

Table 13: Details of mobile measurement tours.

Date	Start (UTC)	End (UTC)	CL61 serial number	Tour details	Comments
22/03/2022	10:55	12:55	T2920393	Intra-urban tour with stops of several minutes at FRIE and WILM	ALC with low laser power, cf. Table 2
28/03/2022	07:30	15:45	T2920393	Along main wind direction (W), driving eastbound to rural area, then westbound into the city; Windsong launches along the way, cf. Figure 11, Table 12	ALC with low laser power, cf. Table 2
29/03/2022	08:15	13:20	T2920393	Along main wind direction (WNW), driving eastbound to rural area, then circling back westbound into the city; Windsong launches along the way, cf. Figure 11, Table 12	ALC with low laser power, cf. Table 2
30/03/2022	05:40	09:15	T2920393	Along main wind direction (N), driving southbound, then circling back northbound into the city; Windsong launches along the way, cf. Figure 11, Table 12	ALC with low laser power, cf. Table 2; premature end due to power inverter issues
11/04/2022	06:59	13:08	T2920393	ALC comparison at WEDD (~2.5 hours), intra-urban tour with stops of several minutes at TEMP, FRIE, and WILM	ALC with low laser power, cf. Table 2
03/08/2022	08:20	11:34	T3250605	Urban-rural tour, preparation for 04/08/2022	
04/08/2022	04:00	22:30	T3250605	Urban-rural tour, stationary at ZOSS from 05:55 to 21:15; multiple Windsong launches at ZOSS, cf. Figure 11, Table 12	
09/08/2022	07:40	10:25	T3250605	Test tour for 11/08/2022, along highway S and E of Berlin, then crossing city	No ALC data after 09:26 due to data transmission failure from ALC to RaspberryPi, tour ended due to malfunction of power inverter
11/08/2022	04:50	14:30	T3250605	Perpendicular to wind direction (NE), crossing city twice in both directions; multiple Windsong launches at RAGO, cf. Figure 11, Table 12	
12/08/2022	07:45	11:15	T3250605	ALC comparison at WEDD (~2.5 hours), intra-urban tour	

3.12 Earth observations (mid-infrared and thermal infrared)

Intensive mid- and thermal-infrared (MTIR) observations took place during the summer IOP with sensors including: three thermal-infrared (TIR) cameras (Optris 640 Pi and Optris 400 Pi) mounted on the ground and a building roof (at site GROB), SatelliteVu mid-infrared (MIR) sensor mounted on an aircraft, and Anafi Parrot thermal sensor mounted on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). This was completed with satellite observations from Sentinel-3 SLSTR, MODIS, ASTER, ECOSTRESS and Landsat. Thus, a wide range of spatial resolution (<1 m to 1 km) data were collected, many over the same location and at the same time (Table 14). The sensors differ in the field of view, their wavelength, and their accuracy.

Table 14: List of satellite/airborne/Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) acquisition times (Berlin local time, UTC+1) for the mid- and thermal-infrared measurements. Bold indicates acquisitions across sensors in a period of less than half an hour.

Date	Landsat 8	Landsat 9	Sentinel-3A	Sentinel-3B	MODIS (Terra)	MODIS (Aqua)	ECOSTRESS	ASTER	Satellite Vu	UAV
01/08/2022			11:14	12:15	11:22	13:01	17:43			
					13:00	14:39				
			22:39	22:01	22:33			22:41	22:15	
02/08/2022			22:13	11:49	12:05	2:32	16:54		16:03	
					21:39	4:09	18:31			
					23:16	13:43				
03/08/2022	12:03		12:01	11:23	11:10	3:14	17:42			11:30
				22:49	12:47	12:49				
					22:21	14:26				
04/08/2022		11:56	11:36	10:57	11:52	2:19	15:17	12:00	11:18	
			23:02	22:23	23:04	3:57	16:54			
						13:30				
05/08/2022			11:10	12:11	10:57	3:01	16:05			
			22:35	21:57	12:35	14:13				
					22:09					
06/08/2022			22:09	11:45	11:40	3:44	15:16			11:30
				23:11	22:51	13:18	16:53			
						14:56				
						2:48				
						4:26				
07/08/2022			11:58	11:19	12:22	14:00	16:04			
				22:45	21:56					
08/08/2022			11:32	10:54	11:27	3:31				
			22:58	22:19	13:05	13:05				
					22:39	14:43				
09/08/2022			11:06	12:07	12:10	2:36	14:27			
			22:31	21:53	21:44	4:13				
					23:22	13:47				
10/08/2022				11:41	11:15	3:18				
				23:08	12:53	14:29				
			22:06		22:26			22:35	21:46	22:00
11/08/2022		12:02	11:54	11:15	11:57	2:23	12:50	12:06		
				23:41	21:32	4:00				
					23:09	13:34				

4 Sites

An overview of all measurement sites is provided in Table 15. Detailed site meta data and instrument deployments are only given for *urbisphere* sites and instrumentation (Section 4.1). Further sites than those given in this report are operated by partner institutions and are available in the region. If possible, references to sites operated by other institutions are included in Section 4.2. Temporary sites operated during the IOPs are presented in Section 4.3.

Table 15: *urbisphere*-Berlin measurement sites and sensors operated on the ground (G) or roof (at given height) at given elevation above sea level (asl). Sites listed are those used in the campaign, further sites in the region are available. Date (DD-MM-YY) with start date (‡) earlier than 01/10/21 and end date (‡) ongoing, but all may have gaps due to outages. Operators are *urbisphere*/University of Freiburg (UFR), Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), Technische Universität Berlin (TUB), Freie Universität Berlin (FUB), Landesbetrieb Forst Brandenburg (LFB), Brandenburg University of Technology (BTU), FUTURE/University of Reading (UR), and HTW Berlin - University of Applied Sciences (HTW).

Site code	Site name	Longitude (° E)	Latitude (° N)	Ring	Elevation (m asl)	Sensor height (m)	Date		Operator	Comment
							Start	End		
ALTL	Altlandsberg	52.557283	13.727988	C	57.5	G	11/11/21	06/07/22	UFR	
ANGE	Angermünde	53.031631	13.990849	C	54.0	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10291
BARU	Baruth	52.061375	13.499704	C	54.9	G	‡	22/06/22	DWD	WMO ID 10376
CHAR	Charlottenburg	52.512745	13.320066	B	33.8	77.8	27/08/21	12/10/22	UFR, TUB	
FICH	Fichtenberg	52.457794	13.310898	B	66.6	10.4	‡	‡	FUB	DWD site “Berlin-Dahlem (FU)”, WMO ID 10381, AERONET site “Berlin_FUB”
FOGR	Forest Grunewald	52.473253	13.225099	B	55.9	G	‡	‡	TUB	
FRIE	Friedrichstadt	52.507556	13.397881	A	34.1	73.7	15/07/21	06/10/22	UFR	
GENT	Genthin	52.387542	12.160061	C	34.9	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10365
GLEI	Gleisdreieck	52.494010	13.376607	A	37.5	G	04/08/22	11/08/22	UFR	
GRGL	Gross Glienicke	52.465286	13.102737	C	44.0	3	10/09/21	10/10/22	UFR	
GRKR	Gross Kreuz	52.403896	12.785645	C	31.3	G	01/09/21	14/10/22	UFR	
GROP	Gropiusstadt	52.422949	13.473843	B	43.8	80.1	26/01/22	20/10/22	UFR, UR	
GRUN	Grunewald	52.488500	13.249440	B	55.2	4.6	10/05/22	17/10/22	UFR	
HELL	Hellersdorf	52.548064	13.585989	B	51.0	G	13/09/21	07/10/22	UFR	
KIEN	Kienhorst	52.973419	13.643776	C	78.1	31.0	‡	‡	LFB	ICOS site DE-Kie
KYRI	Kyritz	52.936310	12.409355	C	40.2	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10267
LICH	Lichtenberg	52.532620	13.490361	B	60.3	G	25/08/21	04/10/22	UFR	
LIND	Lindenberg	52.208532	14.118009	C	97.7	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10393, includes measurements at location “Falkenberg”
MANS	Manschnow	52.546856	14.545148	C	12.0	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10396
MARI	Mariefelde	52.398415	13.368076	B	46.9	2.5	02/09/21	13/10/22	UFR	
MAVI	Märkisches Viertel	52.592138	13.355699	B	47.8	23.3	23/06/22	21/10/22	UFR	
MITT	Mitte	52.523081	13.412517	A	37.1	123.4	31/08/21	11/10/22	UFR	
MUEN	Müncheberg	52.521694	14.129849	C	63.6	G	10/06/22	19/09/22	BTU	
NEUK	Neukölln	52.443652	13.457817	B	35.9	24.9	23/11/22	19/10/22	UFR	
NEUR	Neuruppin	52.903729	12.807121	C	38.4	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10270
OSWE	Oberschöneweide	52.455712	13.524017	B	34.5	27.6	23/11/22	19/10/22	HTW, UFR	
PLAN	Plänterwald	52.483590	13.479983	A	35.0	11.4	23/09/21	04/10/22	UFR	

POTS	Potsdam	52.381108	13.062117	C	80.8	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10379
REIC	Reichenow	52.650763	14.067637	C	70.9	4	11/11/21	07/10/22	UFR	
RAGO	Ragow	52.296605	13.538686	C	44.1	G	11/08/22	11/08/22	UFR	
ROTH	Rothenburgstraße	52.457257	13.315781	B	46.4	G	‡	‡	TUB	ICOS site DE-BeR
SCHO	Schöneberg	52.502927	13.347332	A	35.2	54.4	28/06/22	05/10/22	UR	
TEMP	Tempelhof	52.467502	13.402222	A	47.9	G	20/09/21	05/10/22	DWD, UFR	WMO ID 10384
TUCC	TUB Campus Charlottenburg	52.512238	13.327804	A	34.0	45.4	‡	‡	TUB, UFR	
WEDD	Wedding	52.540129	13.368945	A	35.8	65.5	26/08/21	12/10/22	UFR	
WEIS	Weißensee	52.552620	13.436642	A	48.3	G	21/09/21	11/10/22	UFR	
WEST	Westend	52.524105	13.269433	B	55.7	G	24/09/21	14/10/22	UFR	
WIES	Wiesenburg	52.120703	12.458597	C	187.0	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10368
WILM	Wilmersdorf	52.489598	13.302705	B	45.6	93.8	08/09/21	10/10/22	UFR	
WITT	Wittenberg	51.889181	12.644598	C	104.6	G	‡	‡	DWD	WMO ID 10474
ZOSS	Zossen	52.232072	13.357386	C	49.3	G	04/08/22	04/08/22	UFR	

4.1 *urbisphere* sites

The following subsections provide details of each measurement site operated by *urbisphere*.

During the campaign, data quick looks were operationally created for each device and consulted each day to check for instrument malfunctions or failures.

All *urbisphere* sites underwent regular maintenance at 2-3 weekly intervals. In case of instrument malfunction or failure an unscheduled maintenance was carried out following as soon as possible and mostly within a few days after the identified malfunction/failure. During all maintenance events, safety-related aspects (e.g., bolts, guy wires, weights) and the functionality of all instruments were checked. For each event, handwritten log sheets were filled in and photos taken. The maintenance logs were digitalised in the form of (machine-readable) spreadsheets per site (Fenner et al. 2024).

Maintenance details in each spreadsheet are grouped according to instrument type (e.g. ALC, DWL). As an example, at site MAVI an ALC, a sun tracker with radiometers and an AWS (ClimaVUE50) was deployed. Maintenance details for the ALC are given in columns H to K, for the sun tracker with radiometers in columns X to AF, and for the AWS in columns AK to AQ. The remaining columns are empty but present, so that each spreadsheet has identical column names.

It is highly recommended that the spreadsheet is consulted when working with the measurement data.

4.1.1 ALTL (Altlandsberg)

General site information	
Site name	Altlandsberg
Site code	ALTL
Address	Alexander-Giertz-Straße 12, D-15345 Altlandsberg
Latitude (° N)	52.557283
Longitude (° E)	13.727988
Type of site	Ground-based
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	57.47
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	Rural ALC site along the main transect NE of Berlin
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site (16/12/2021)

Panorama photograph (06/07/2022)

N

E

S

W

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments (08/06/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-11-11 13:01/ 2022-07-06 09:35	Ceilmeter; Vaisala; CL61; T2950755	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 100000004150af65	0/0/0	0	2021-11-11 Firmware 1.0; 2022-06-08 Firmware 1.1.6	2021-11-11 File length 15 minutes (60 profiles per file, each 15 sec); 2021-06-08 File length 5 minutes (20 profiles per file, each 15 sec);	

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-11-11	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T2950755; Raspberry Pi, 4, 100000004150af65
2022-07-06	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.2 CHAR (Charlottenburg)

General site information	
Site name	Charlottenburg
Site code	CHAR
Address	Ernst-Reuter-Platz 10, D-10587 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.512745
Type of site	13.320066
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	33.82
Station offset (m agl)	77.78
Purpose of site	Roof-top site for LAS transmitters at inner-city location
Operator	University of Freiburg; Technische Universität Berlin

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

31/08/2021

02/12/2021

Comments

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

BLS2000 transmitter (02/12/2021)

BLS450 transmitter (12/04/2022)

View of BLS2000 transmitter (20/07/2022)

View of BLS450 transmitter (20/07/2022)

Comments

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-08-31 13:00 / 2022-10-12 10:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS450; T-E-1059	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1050 (WILM)	3/0/0	205	boost: OFF, long path: OFF;	2021-09-08 SRun-Scin 1.66 at WILM	All LEDs remained active until end of deployment; BLS450 receiver at WILM
2	2021-08-31 16:00 / 2022-07-20 10:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1078	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1082 (MITT)	3/0/2	80	boost: ON, long path: OFF	2021-09-02 SRun-Scin 1.66 at MITT	All LEDs remained active until end of deployment; BLS2000 receiver at MITT
3	2022-07-20 10:01 / 2022-08-22 10:30	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1075	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1051 (MITT)	3/0/2	80	boost: ON, long path: OFF	2022-07-21 SRun-Scin 1.67 at MITT	Upgraded transmitter; Tried (and failed) alignment with upgraded BLS2000 system at MITT; BLS2000 receiver at MITT

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-08-31	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1059; Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1078
2022-07-20	End deployment: BLS2000 SN T-E-1078 Start deployment: BLS2000 SN T-E-1075
2022-08-22	End deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-107
2022-10-12	End deployment: All remaining equipment

4.1.3 FRIE (Friedrichstadt)

General site information	
Site name	Friedrichstadt
Site code	FRIE
Address	Axel-Springer-Straße 65, D-10888 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	52.507556
Longitude (° E)	13.397881
Type of site	Roof-top
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	34.05
Station offset (m agl)	73.65
Purpose of site	Inner-city, central location of measurement network at intersection between main and perpendicular ALC-DWL transects for comprehensive, multi-instrument measurements
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

Panorama photograph (30/06/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (06/10/2022)	
Comments	<p>Parts of building taller than roof top with instruments, causing horizon obstruction for radiometer measurements W of instruments.</p> <p>Several antennas and poles on roof top with potential influence on radiation measurements (cf. fish-eye image).</p> <p>Building heating/cooling system on taller roof top W of instruments.</p>

Photographs of instruments

DWL, Sun photometer, Sun tracker, ClimaVUE50 (15/07/2021)

Sun photometer (21/01/2022)

BLS2000 receiver, ClimaVUE50 (26/11/2021)

DWL (22/07/2021)

Sun tracker (12/11/2021)

Comments

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation , Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-07-15 10:00 / 2022-10-01 18:08	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 175	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 175	1.1/0/0	0	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi; 2021-07-15 10:00 UTC: Focus = 800 m for all active scan patterns; 2022-06-22 18:12 UTC: Focus = 1500 m for all active scan patterns; 2022-06-22 18:18 UTC: Focus = 2000 m for all active scan patterns; 2022-06-24 12:19 UTC: Focus = Infinity for all active scan patterns; 2022-07-05 10:00 UTC: Focus = 2000 m for all active scan patterns; 2022-07-06: Focus = 2000 m for Stare (and all other) scan patterns in daily scan scheduler	2021-07-15 StreamLine XR v14-6.vi; 2021-07-15 12-point VAD scan every 5 minutes at 75° elevation angle, 6-point VAD wind-profile scan every 10 minutes at 75° elevation, rest Stare at 90° elevation angle; 2022-06-29 9 UTC: 12-point VAD scan and 6-point VAD WindProfile scan set to 11 minute interval; 2022-07-04 08 UTC: 12- point VAD scan every 5 minutes, 6-point VAD wind- profile scan every 10 minutes; 2022-07-06 Modified scan pattern to daily scan scheduler, 12-point VAD at 75° elevation every 10 minutes, RHI from -2° to 182° elevation at 250° azimuth (continuous) at HH:58:00 until full hour, rest Stare (2000 m focus, 667 gates, 18 m gate length, 3 s/ray); 2022-08-01 11:45 Updated scan schedule with 12-point VAD scan at 75° elevation now every 5 minutes, rest as before	
2	2021-09-14 12:00 / 2022-04-05 07:42	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec;	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing	2/1/2	331	-	2021-09-14 SRun-Scin 1.66; 1-minute mean values stored	

		BLS2000; T-E-1076	Unit (SPU)/ Scintec/ SPU19001/ T-E-1083					
3	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Sun tracker; Kipp and Zonen; SOLYS2; 200613	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	0.82/-4/-2	-	-	-	2021-08-03 additional power unit for ventilation and heating of radiometers installed
4	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Pyrheliometer; Kipp and Zonen; CHP1; 190791	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1.5/-4.02/-2	-	Calibration: 12/12/2019; Sun tracker	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 6-second samples, averaged to and stored as 1-minute values	2021-10-11 Desiccant changed
5	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 990642	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1.5/-4.03/-2	-	Calibration: 17/11/2020; Sun tracker, not shaded, ventilated, heated	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 6-second samples, averaged to and stored as 1-minute values	2021-08-20 New white ventilation unit/housing installed; 2021-10-08 Desiccant changed; 2022-02-10 New white radiation shield/cover without gap between dome and shield installed
6	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM2; 990643	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1.5/-4.01/-2	-	Calibration: 15/10/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 6-second samples, averaged to and stored as 1-minute values	2021-08-20 New white ventilation unit/housing installed; 2021-10-11 Desiccant changed; 2022-02-10 New white radiation shield/cover without gap between dome and shield installed
7	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2021-08-20 09:00	Pyrgeometer; Kipp and Zonen; CG1; 000206	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1.5/-4.04/-2	-	Calibration: 17/11/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 6-second samples, averaged to and stored as 1-minute values	
8	2021-08-20 12:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Pyrgeometer; Kipp and Zonen; CGR4; 120530	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1.5/-4.04/-2	-	Calibration: 13/11/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 6-second samples, averaged to and stored as 1-minute values	2021-10-11 Desiccant changed; 2022-02-10 New white radiation shield/cover without gap between dome and shield installed
9	2021-08-03 15:00 /	Sun sensor; Kipp and Zonen; Sun sensor; 210618	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1.5/-4/-2	-	Sun tracker		

	2022-10-06 08:00							
10	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	GPS antenna; Campbell Scientific; GPS16x-HVS; 1A4287534	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	1/-4/-2	-		2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples	Set up for time synchronisation
11	2021-07-15 15:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Weather station; Campbell Scientific; ClimaVUE50; VUE-500002464	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16945	2.68/1/2	0		2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 10-second samples, averaged to and stored as 1-minute values	
12	2021-07-15 10:00 / 2022-10-06 08:00	Sun sky lunar multispectral photometer; CIMEL; CE318- T; 1240	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 12376867816438724 62	1/-5/2	-	Calibration: 05/08/2020 (AERONET), 13/11/2020 (ACTRIS)		Built-in GPS with issues obtaining GPS fix at times.

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-07-15	Start deployment: Halo Photonics, StreamLine, 175; Kipp&Zonen, SOLYS2, 200613; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 990642; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 990643; Kipp&Zonen, CG1, 000206; Kipp&Zonen, CHP1, 190791; CIMEL, CE318-T, 1240; Raspberry Pi, 4, 1237686781643872462; Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002464
2021-08-03	Start deployment: Halo Photonics, StreamLine, 175; Sun sensor at Sun tracker
2021-08-20	Start deployment: Kipp&Zonen, CGR4, 120530
2021-09-14	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1076
2021-12-02	End deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, SPU
2022-10-06	End deployment: All remaining equipment

4.1.4 GRGL (Gross Glienecke)

General site information	
Site name	Gross Glienicke
Site code	GRGL
Address	Christophorusweg 8, D-14476 Potsdam
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.465286
Type of site	13.102737
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	44
Station offset (m agl)	3
Purpose of site	ALC site on the main transect, SW of Berlin in small town/rural
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

10/10/2022

Panorama photograph (13/06/2022)

W

N

E

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (10/10/2022)

N

E

W

S

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

CL61, looking SW, with private weather station in foreground (10/09/2021)

CL61, looking SE (10/09/2021)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-10 12:00 / 2022-07-12 10:10	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3250605	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3250605	3/0/0	0	2021-09-10 v1.0, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 60; 2022-07-05 v1.1.10, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 20;	2021-09-10 v1.0; 2021-09-10 FTP data transfer to server; 2022-07-05 v1.1.10;	2022-07-05 Transmitter laser power alarm, 47 % laser power; 2022-07-12 returned to Vaisala for repair
2	2022-07-12 10:30 / 2022-10-10 10:15	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T2950755	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 100000004150af65	30/0	0	2022-07-12 v1.1.10, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 20;	2022-07-12 FTP data transfer from CL61	

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-10-09	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T3250605
2022-07-12	End deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T3250605 due to low transmitter laser power Start Deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T2950755 Start deployment: Raspberry Pi, 4
2022-10-10	End deployment: All remaining equipment

4.1.5 GRKR (Gross Kreuzt)

General site information	
Site name	Gross Kreuzt
Site code	GRKR
Address	Lakenweg 15, D-14550 Groß Kreuzt (Havel)
Latitude (° N)	Ground-based
Longitude (° E)	52.403896
Type of site	12.785645
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	31.25
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	Rural ALC site at the SW end of the main transect
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

01/09/2021

03/11/2021

Directional views (01/09/2022)

N

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (14/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

CL31 (10/12/2021)

CL31, looking SW (14/10/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-01 12:30 / 2022-10-10 10:00	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL31; B20202	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 10000000d8bb7d db	0/0/0	0	2021-09-01 v3.000; 2021-09-01 reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_ h2 = on		2021-11-16 Window blower removed (only heating, not blowing), installed window blower

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-01	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, B20202; Raspberry Pi, 4, 10000000d8bb7ddb
2021-10-14	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.6 GROP (Gropiusstadt)

General site information	
Site name	Gropiusstadt
Site code	GROP
Address	Joachim-Gottschalk-Weg 1, D-12353 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.422949
Type of site	13.473843
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	43.83
Station offset (m agl)	80.07
Purpose of site	Site at S/SE boundary of built-up area for Sun tracker, LAS receivers, TIR cameras, IRTs
Operator	University of Freiburg; University of Reading

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

08/08/2022

Directional views (25/04/2022)

N

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (14/10/2022)

Comments

Several poles on roof top with potential influence on radiation measurements (cf. fish-eye image).

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

Sun tracker, BLS2000 receiver, ClimaVUE50, BLS450 receiver, looking S (29/04/2022)

BLS450 receiver, ClimaVUE50, BLS2000 receiver, Sun tracker, looking NW (04/03/2022)

TIR cameras looking SW and NW, IRT in white tube (20/10/2022)

TIR cameras looking NE and SE, IRT in white tube (20/10/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2022-01-26 10:00 / 2022-07-28 11:40	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1077	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E- 1081	1/0/0	43	2022-01-26 Dip switches 2 & 6	2022-01-26 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	Transmitter at OSWE
2	2022-01-26 10:00 / 2022-05-25 09:45	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec; BLS450; T-E-1055	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E- 1056	1/0/-2	335	2022-01-26 dip switches 1 & 5; 2022-02-24 dip switches 2 & 6;	2022-01-26 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	Transmitter at NEUK; 2022-05-25 Deployment ended since transmitter dismounted
3	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-08-02 08:00	Weather station; Campbell Scientific; ClimaVUE50; VUE-500002552	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	1.5/0/-2	0		2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 10- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	Potentially issues with wind speed and direction due to low height above roof level
4	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Sun tracker; Kipp and Zonen; SOLYS2; 210712	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	0.8/0/2	-	-	-	-
5	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Pyrheliometer; Kipp and Zonen; CHP1; 210927	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	0.8/0/2	-	Calibration: 25/11/2020; Sun tracker	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
6	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Sun sensor; Kipp and Zonen; Sun sensor; 210619	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	0.7/0/2	-	Sun tracker	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
7	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 990645	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	0.83/0/2	-	Calibration: 15/10/2020; Sun tracker, not shaded, ventilated, heated	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	

8	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 940204	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	0.83/0/2	-	Calibration: 15/10/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
9	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Pyrgeometer; Kipp and Zonen; CG1; 000206	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	0.83/0/2	-	Calibration: 17/11/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
10	2022-01-28 12:30 / 2022-10-20 07:30	GPS antenna/ Campbell Scientific/ GPS16x-HVS/ 1A4283967	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16937	1/0/-2	-		2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples	Set up for time synchronisation
11	2022-07-28 14:50 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec; BLS450; T-E-1054	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E- 1051	1/0/-2	335	2022-07-28 dip switches 2 & 6;	2022-07-28 SRun-Scin 1.67, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	Transmitter at NEUK
12	2022-07-28 14:50 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver/ Scintec/ BLS2000/ T-E- 1077	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E- 1081	1/0/0	43	2022-07-28 Dip switches 2 & 6	2022-07-28 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	New transmitter at OSWE and after temporary check with BLS900 at NEUK
13	2022-07-31 10:00 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Infrared Thermometer/ Campbell Scientific/ IR120/ E1631	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR3000; 7617	1/0/5	-		2022-07-31 10-second sampling, averaged and logged at 1 minute	Installed an southern side of TIR camera stand on eastern side of building, pointing downward
14	2022-07-31 10:00 / 2022-10-20 07:30	Infrared Thermometer/ Campbell Scientific/ IR120/ E1633	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR3000; 7617	1/0/-5	-		2022-07-31 10-second sampling, averaged and logged at 1 minute	Installed an southern side of TIR camera stand on western side of building, pointing downward
15	2022-07-22 12:00 / 2022-10-20 07:30	7 - 14 micron thermal camera/ Optris/ PI-160/ 12080017	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 10000000d03175fd	1.5/1/-5	310		60-second sampling and storage	Facing: NW, zenith angle 150°
16	2022-07-22 12:00 /	7 - 14 micron thermal camera/	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi	1.5/-1/-5	230		60-second sampling and storage	Facing: SW, zenith angle 150°

	2022-10-20 07:30	Optris/ PI-160/ 12080103	Foundation; 4; 10000007d6362f0					
17	2022-07-22 12:00 / 2022-10-20 07:30	7 - 14 micron thermal camera/ Optris/ PI-160/ 12080019	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 10000009c1aa96b	1.5/1/5	50		60-second sampling and storage	Facing: NE, zenith angle 150°
18	2022-07-22 12:00 / 2022-10-20 07:30	7 - 14 micron thermal camera/ Optris/ PI-160/ 12070069	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000600a92e6	1.5/-1/5	130		60-second sampling and storage	Facing: SE, zenith angle 150°

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2022-01-26	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1077; Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1055; Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002552; Kipp&Zonen, SOLYS2, 210712; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 990645; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 940204; Kipp&Zonen, CG1, 000206; Kipp&Zonen, CHP1, 210927; Kipp&Zonen, Sun sensor, 210619
2022-02-04	Mounted: New lightning strike poles (two)
2022-02-24	Dismounted: New lightning strike poles became loose, poles dismantled
2022-03-04	Mounted: New lightning strike poles (two)
2022-05-25	End deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1055, dismantled receiver and SPU
2022-07-28	Start deployment: TIR cameras
2022-07-29	Start deployment: Campbell Scientific, IR120, E1631; Campbell Scientific, IR120, E1633; Campbell Scientific, CR3000, 7671
2022-08-02	End deployment: Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002552 Start deployment: Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002835
2022-08-05	Mounted: Campbell Scientific IR120, E1631 & Campbell Scientific IR120, E1633, lightning protection was mounted on IR-stand
2022-10-20	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.7 GRUN (Grunewald)

General site information	
Site name	Grunewald
Site code	GRUN
Address	Königsweg 6, D-14193 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.4885
Type of site	13.24944
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	55.15
Station offset (m agl)	4.61
Purpose of site	Radiation flux site on main transect at WSW boundary of built-up area of Berlin
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site (24/06/2022)

Panorama photograph (24/06/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (14/10/2022)

Comments | Several poles on roof top with potential influence on radiation measurements (cf. images).

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

ClimaVUE50 and Sun tracker, looking NNE (17/10/2022)

Sun tracker and ClimaVUE50, looking W (10/05/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation , Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Sun tracker; Kipp and Zonen; SOLYS2; 210708	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.64/0/0	-	-	-	-
2	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Sun sensor; Kipp and Zonen; Sun sensor; 210662	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.55/0/0	-	Sun tracker	-	-
3	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-05-25 08:30	Pyrheliometer; Kipp and Zonen; CHP1; 210924	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.64/0/0	-	Calibration: 30/11/2021; Sun tracker	2022-05-10 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	2022-05-25 Deployment end due to systematically low values during clear-sky conditions compared to other sites -> Misalignment? Exchanged with CHP1 SN 210925
4	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 010867	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.73/0/0	-	Calibration: 15/10/2020; Sun tracker, not shaded, ventilated, heated	2022-05-10 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	-
5	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 990644	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.73/0/0	-	Calibration: 17/11/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2022-05-10 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	-
6	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Pyrgeometer; Kipp and Zonen; CG1; 000203	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.73/0/0	-	Calibration: 23/11/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2022-05-10 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	-
7	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Weather station; Campbell Scientific; ClimaVUE50; VUE- 500002850	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	2.04/1/-1	0	-	2022-05-10 OS 5.01, 10- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	-
8	2022-05-25 08:31 / 2022-10-17 08:00	Pyrheliometer; Kipp and Zonen; CHP1; 210925	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.64/0/0	-	Calibration: 30/11/2021; Sun tracker	2022-05-25 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	Replacement for 210924

9	2022-05-10 12:20 / 2022-10-17 08:00	GPS antenna; Campbell Scientific; GPS16x-HVS; 1A4287675	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16941	0.5/1/-1	-	-	2022-05-10 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples	Set up for time synchronisation
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Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2022-05-10	Start deployment: Kipp&Zonen, SOLYS2, 210708; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 010867; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 990644; Kipp&Zonen, CG1, 000203; Kipp&Zonen, CHP1, 210924; Kipp&Zonen, Sun sensor, 210662; Campbell Scientific, CR1000X, 16941; Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002850
2022-05-25	End deployment: Kipp&Zonen, CHP1, 210924 Start deployment: Kipp&Zonen, CHP1, 210925
2022-10-17	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.8 HELL (Hellersdorf)

General site information	
Site name	Hellersdorf
Site code	HELL
Address	Zossener Straße 26, D-12629 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Ground-based
Longitude (° E)	52.548064
Type of site	13.585989
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	51.03
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	ALC site on the main transect at NE boundary of built-up area of Berlin
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site (07/10/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (07/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments (07/10/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-13 09:00 / 2022-06-08 09:00	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3120614	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3120614	0/0/0	0	2021-09-13 Firmware v1.0, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 60	2021-09-13 Firmware v1.0, FTP data transfer to server	-
2	2022-06-08 09:01 / 2022-10-07 08:00	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3120614	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 100000007a936f51	0/0/0	0	2022-06-08 Firmware v1.1.6, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 60; 2022-07-06 Firmware v1.1.10, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 20;	2022-06-08 FTP data transfer from CL61	-

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-13	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T3120614
2022-06-08	Start deployment: Raspberry Pi, 4, 100000007a936f51
2022-10-07	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.9 LICH (Lichtenberg)

General site information	
Site name	Lichtenberg
Site code	LICH
Address	Landsberger Allee 230, D-10367 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Ground-based
Longitude (° E)	52.53262
Type of site	13.490361
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	60.3
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	DWL site on main transect, NE of city centre
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

25/08/2021

Panorama photograph (08/06/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (01/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

DWL setup at initial deployment, looking S (28/09/2021)

DWL setup with reflective foil around and new position of power unit after 04/08/2022, looking E (08/08/2021)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-08-25 09:00 / 2022-10-01 18:04	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 204	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 204	0/0/0	0	2021-08-25 StreamLine XR v14-6.vi; 2021-08-25 Focus = 800 m for all active scan patterns; 2022-07-06 Focus = 2000 m for all active scan patterns	2021-08-25 StreamLine XR v14-6.vi; 2021-08-25 12-point VAD scan every 5 minutes at 75° elevation angle, 6-point VAD wind-profile scan every 10 minutes at 75° elevation, rest Stare at 90° elevation angle; 2022-07-06 Modified scan pattern to daily scan scheduler, 12-point VAD at 75° elevation every 10 minutes, RHI from -2° to 182° elevation at 250° azimuth (continuous) at HH:58:00 until full hour, rest Stare (2000 m focus, 667 gates, 18 m gate length, 3 s/ray); 2022-08-01 11:45 Updated scan schedule with 12-point VAD scan at 75° elevation now every 5 minutes, rest as before	Instrument with overheating issues (power supply), switching off during hot weather.

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-08-25	Start deployment: Halo Photonics, StreamLine, 204
2022-08-04	Installed reflective foil around power supply and positioned power supply north of DWL to avoid overheating
2022-10-04	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.10 MARI (Marienfelde)

General site information	
Site name	Marienfelde
Site code	MARI
Address	Schichauweg 66, D-12307 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.398415
Type of site	13.368076
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	46.94
Station offset (m agl)	2.5
Purpose of site	ALC site at S/SW tip of intra-urban grid, at southern boundary of built-up area of Berlin
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

02/09/2021

03/12/2021

Directional views (26/10/2021)

N

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (13/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instruments

CL31 after initial deployment (02/09/2021)

CL31 with bird spikes after 08/10/2021, looking SW (19/11/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-02 07:00/ 2022-10- 13 08:00	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL31; S2010718	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 10000000e7a9e1 38	2.5/0/0	0	2021-09-02 v3.000; 2021-09-02 reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_ h2 = on		

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-02	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, S2010718; Raspberry Pi, 4, 10000000e7a9e138
2022-10-13	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.11 MAVI (Märkisches Viertel)

General site information	
Site name	Maerkisches Viertel
Site code	MAVI
Address	Dannenwalder Weg 144, D-13439 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.592138
Type of site	13.355699
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	47.81
Station offset (m agl)	23.27
Purpose of site	ALC and Sun tracker site at N end of perpendicular transect, at N boundary of built-up area
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

Looking E (23/06/2022)

Looking S (23/06/2022)

Panorama photograph (23/06/2022)

W

N

E

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (21/10/2022)

Comments | Part of building taller than ClimaVUE50, W of instrument, potential influence on wind measurements

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instruments

Sun tracker, looking S/SW (21/10/2022)

ClimaVUE50 and CL31, looking W (23/06/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation , Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Ceilmeter; Vaisala; CL31; S2010719	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000031122a6a	0/0/0	0	2021-09-02 v3.000; 2021-09-02 reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = on		
2	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Weather station; Campbell Scientific; ClimaVUE50; VUE- 500002851	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	2.05/-1/0	0	-	2022-06-23 OS 5.01, 10- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	Potentially issues with wind speed and direction from W to N due to building
3	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Sun tracker; Kipp and Zonen; SOLYS2; 210713	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.65/ -5/5	-	-	-	
4	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Sun sensor; Kipp and Zonen; Sun sensor; 210609	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.55/ -5/5/	-	Sun tracker	-	
5	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Pyrheliometer; Kipp and Zonen; CHP1; 210926	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.65/ -5/ 5	-	Calibration: 25/11/2021; Sun tracker	2022-06-23 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
6	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 041181	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.73/-5/5/	-	Calibration: 15/10/2020; Sun tracker, not shaded, ventilated, heated	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
7	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Pyranometer; Kipp and Zonen; CM21; 930104	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.73/ -5/5	-	Calibration: 15/10/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
8	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	Pyrgeometer; Kipp and Zonen; CG1; 010238	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.73/ -5/ 5	-	Calibration: 23/11/2020; Sun tracker, shaded (ball), ventilated, heated	2022-01-28 OS 5.01, 6- second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	
9	2022-06-23 13:00 / 2022-10-21 08:00	GPS antenna;Campbell Scientific; GPS16x- HVS; 1A4287682	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16942	0.5/0/0	-	-	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples	Set up for time synchronisation

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2022-06-23	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, S2010719; Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000031122a6a; Kipp&Zonen, SOLYS2, 210713; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 041181; Kipp&Zonen, CM21, 930104; Kipp&Zonen, CG1, 010238; Kipp&Zonen, CHP1, 210926; Kipp&Zonen, Sun sensor, 210609; Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002851; Campbell Scientific, CR1000X, 16942
2022-10-21	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.12 MITT (Mitte)

General site information	
Site name	Mitte
Site code	MITT
Address	Alexanderplatz 7, D-10178 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.523081
Type of site	13.412517
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	37.05
Station offset (m agl)	113.35 (bottom roof level)
Purpose of site	Inner-city turbulent flux measurements (eddy covariance and LAS)
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

Top level with IRGASON, looking SW (20/12/2021)

Bottom level with LAS receivers, looking NW (20/12/2021)

Panorama photograph/directional views

Top level (20/12/2021)

Top level, looking NW (17/12/2021)

Top level, looking SE (01/02/2022)

Comments	<p>Site at two levels of the building: lower level (~113 m agl) with LAS receivers and top level (~123 m agl) with IRGASON. At the top level there is a steel construction with a steel wall around it, ~6 m tall.</p> <p>Two tall antennas (~35 m) are on the building roof.</p> <p>Potential influence of building on IRGASON measurements, azimuth angles 35° - 215° (likely) not usable.</p>
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Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instruments

LAS receivers after initial deployment (17/12/2021)

LAS receivers on modified lower and narrower stand (27/04/2022)

View of the BLS2000 receiver, looking W (09/05/2022)

View of the BLS450 receiver, looking N (09/05/2022)

IRGASON, looking SW (22/08/2022)

IRGASON, looking NW (09/02/2022)

IRGASON, looking NW (20/12/2021)

IRGASON, as seen from ground level
(20/12/2022)

IRGASON above metal “wall”, as seen from bottom level (21/07/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-02 14:00 / 2022-07-15 00:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec; BLS450; T-E-1054	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1051	1.4/0/0	303	2021-09-02 Dip switches: 1 & 5, vertical offset 1.4 m 2022-02-09: Vertical offset 1 m;	2021-09-02 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	Transmitter at WEDD (faulty LED module); Vibration of stand before 2022-02-09 at high wind speeds
2	2021-09-02 14:00 / 2022-07-21 08:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1074	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1082	1.4/0/0	260	2021-09-02 Dip switches: 2 & 6, vertical offset 1.4 m 2022-02-09: Vertical offset 1 m;	2021-09-02 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	Transmitter at CHAR; Vibration of stand before 2022-02-09 at high wind speeds
3	2022-07-21 09:00 / 2022-08-22 13:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Receiver; Scintec; BLS2000/ T-E-1076	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1051	1/0/0	260	2022-07-21 Dip switches: 2 & 6, vertical offset 1 m;	2021-09-02 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	Transmitter at CHAR; Manufacturer-upgraded system, never worked.
4	2021-12-17 13:00 / 2022-10-11 08:00	Integrated CO2 and H2O Open-Path Gas Analyzer and 3-D Sonic Anemometer/ Campbell Scientific/ IRGASON/ 1759	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 27220	12.7/0/0	305	-	2021-12-17 OS 5.01, 20 Hz sampling, data storage at 20 Hz and 30 minutes (EASYFLUX programme); 2022-02-01 New logger programme, same sampling	Mast extending 2.7 m above top of roof construction. Mast (not IRGASON) 1.05 m "inward" of north-western roof edge.
5	2021-12-17 13:00 / 2022-10-11 08:00	GPS antenna; Campbell Scientific; GPS16x-HVS; 1A4283775	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 27220	1/0/0	-	-	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples; 2022-02-01 New logger programme, same sampling	Set up for time synchronisation

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-08-31	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1054; Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1074
2021-12-17	Start deployment: Campbell Scientific, IRGASON, 1759; Campbell Scientific, CR1000X, 27220
2022-07-21	End deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1054; Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1074 Start deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1076
2022-08-22	End deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1076
2022-10-11	End deployment: All remaining equipment

4.1.13 NEUK (Neukölln)

General site information	
Site name	Neukölln
Site code	NEUK
Address	Grüner Weg 13, D-12359 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.443652
Type of site	13.457817
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	35.87
Station offset (m agl)	24.88
Purpose of site	Roof-top site for LAS transmitter at outer-city location
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site

23/11/2021

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instruments

BLS450 transmitter, looking S towards GROF (17/02/2022)

BLS900 transmitter, looking N (19/10/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-11-23 14:00 / 2022-05-19 08:15	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS450; T-E-1061	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1056	0.5/0/0	155	2021-11-23 boost: OFF, long-path: OFF	-	BLS450 receiver at GROF. 2022-03-31 07:00 UTC New LED module installed, old with 2 LED off. 2022-05-19 6 LEDs off and two with low intensity.
2	2022-07-28 11:42 / 2022-10-19 08:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS900; T-E-0609	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1081	0.5/0/0	155	2021-11-23 boost: OFF, long-path: OFF	-	BLS450 receiver at GROF. 2022-10-19 All LED working.

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-11-23	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1061
2022-05-19	End deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1061
2022-07-28	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS900, T-E-0609
2022-10-19	End deployment: Scintec, BLS900, T-E-0609

4.1.14 OSWE (Oberschöneweide)

General site information	
Site name	Oberschöneweide
Site code	OSWE
Address	HTW Berlin - Building G, D-12459 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.455712
Type of site	13.524017
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	34.51
Station offset (m agl)	27.6
Purpose of site	Roof-top site with LAS transmitter at outer-city location, further measurements by HTW
Operator	University of Freiburg; HTW Berlin, University of Applied Sciences

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site

17/02/2022

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instruments

Sun tracker (operator: HTW) and BLS2000 transmitter, looking SW towards GROF (23/11/2021)

BLS2000 transmitter with Sun tracker (left, operator: HTW) and AWS (right, operator: HTW) (28/07/2022, 23/11/2021)

Comments | Additional measurements by HTW with Sun tracker and AWS (<https://wetter.htw-berlin.de/>)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation , Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-11-23 15:00 / 2022-07-08 12:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1079	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1081	0.5/0/0	233	2021-11-23 boost: ON, long-path: OFF	-	BLS2000 receiver at GROUPE. 2022-02-17: 1 LED off. 2022-05-19: 1 LED off.
2	2022-07-28 14:50 / 2022-10-19 09:00	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1078	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1081	0.5/0/0	233	2022-07-28 boost: ON, long-path: OFF	-	BLS2000 receiver at GROUPE. 2022-10-19 All LED working.

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2022-11-23	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1079
2022-07-28	End deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1079 Start deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1078
2022-10-19	End deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1078

4.1.15 PLAN (Plänterwald)

General site information	
Site name	Plänterwald
Site code	PLAN
Address	Neue Krugallee 2-6, D-12435 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.48359
Type of site	13.479983
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	34.99
Station offset (m agl)	11.4
Purpose of site	ALC site at SE tip of intra-urban grid
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

Looking E (24/03/2022)

Looking N (12/11/2021)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (04/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph of instrument

CL31 (23/09/2021)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-23 08:30 / 2022-10-04 10:02	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL31; S2010716	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 100000006e4c65f9	8/0/0	0	2021-09-23 Firmware v3.000, reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = ON		

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-03	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, S2010716; Raspberry Pi, 4, 100000006e4c65f9
2022-10-04	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.16 REIC (Reichenow)

General site information	
Site name	Reichenow
Site code	REIC
Address	Neue Dorfstraße 7, D-15345 Reichenow-Möglin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.650763
Type of site	14.067637
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	70.85
Station offset (m agl)	4
Purpose of site	ALC site at NE end of main transect in rural setting
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site (03/02/2022)

Directional views (04/01/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (07/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instrument

CL31, looking N (02/05/2022)

CL31 (07/10/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-11-11 09:00/ 2022-02-11 08:50	Ceilmeter; Vaisala; CL31; S2010715	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000081ea1c68	4/0/0	0	2021-11-11 Firmware v3.000, reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = ON	Logger with time syncing issues due to bad GSM connection. Logger with power connection issues, leading to many restarts.	Many data gaps.
2	2022-02-11 11:00/ 2022-10-07 10:00	Ceilmeter; Vaisala; CL31; S2010715	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000002f86fc6	4/0/0	0	2022-02-11 Firmware v3.000, reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = ON		Continues previous CL31 deployment ID with new logger.

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-11-11	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, S2010715; Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000081ea1c68
2022-02-11	End deployment: Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000081ea1c68 Start deployment: Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000002f86fc6
2022-10-07	End deployment: all remaining equipment

4.1.17 SCHO (Schöneberg)

General site information	
Site name	Schöneberg
Site code	SCHO
Address	Kurfürstenstraße 114-116, D-10787 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.502927
Type of site	13.347332
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	35.18
Station offset (m agl)	54.4
Purpose of site	Roof-top site for DWL measurements of wakes induced by tall building cluster
Operator	University of Reading, University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site (28/06/2022)

Panorama photograph (28/06/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (05/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instrument

DWL, looking S (05/10/2022)

DWL lidar head with tall-building cluster in background, looking W (28/06/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2022-06-28 11:30 / 2022-10-05 10:00	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 03	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 03	1.5/0/0	23	2022-06-28 Focus ~500 m (manual setting)	2022-06-28 StreamLine XR v14-8.vi, every 18 minutes PPI scan at 0° elevation angle through azimuth angles 150°-310° at 2° resolution. Remainder of the time “Stare” at 90° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray.	Instrument potentially has a negative offset.

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2022-06-28	Start deployment: Halo Photonics, StreamLine, 03
2022-10-05	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.18 TEMP (Tempelhof)

General site information	
Site name	Tempelhof
Site code	TEMP
Address	Tempelhofer Feld, Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Ground-based
Longitude (° E)	52.467502
Type of site	13.402222
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	47.89
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	ALC measurements at inner-city site on perpendicular transect, further measurements by DWD
Operator	Deutscher Wetterdienst; University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

Looking NW (05/10/2022)

Panorama photograph (30/06/2022)

W

N

E

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (05/10/2022)

Comments | Construction work at site (digging), 12/2021 - 09/2022

Measurement setup

Photograph(s) of instruments

CL61 after initial deployment, looking N/NW (20/09/2022)

CL61 with IRT sensors, looking E (30/06/2022)

CL31 with IRT sensors, looking E (29/04/2022)

CL31 head with IRT sensors (white tubes), looking N (28/03/2022)

Comments

Comprehensive further measurements by DWD.
New ALC (Lufft CHM15k) and completely new AWS installed by DWD in September 2022.

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation , Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-20 11:00 / 2022-03-21 10:30	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T2920393	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T2920393	0/0/0	0	2021-09-20 Firmware v1.0, algo.llaveraging.interval = 3, algo.llaveraging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 60	2021-09-20 Firmware v1.0, FTP data transfer to server	2022-03-21 Low transmitter laser power detected, returned to Vaisala for repair
2	2022-06-14 09:00 / 2022-10-05 07:30	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T2920393	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 10000000845c9e70	0/0/0	0	2022-06-14 Firmware v1.1.10, algo.llaveraging.interval = 3, algo.llaveraging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 20	2022-07-12 FTP data transfer from CL61	
3	2022-03-21 11:30 / 2022-06-14 07:30	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL31; S2010719	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000031122a6a	0/0/0	0	2022-03-21 Firmware v3.000, reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = on		2022-06-14 Deployment ended in exchange for CL61 (T2920393)
4	2022-03-28 10:00 / 2022-10-05 07:30	Infrared Thermometer; Campbell Scientific; IR120; E1627	Data logger; Campbell Scientific/ CR3000; 1307	1.5/-1/-1	135; Zenith: 85	-	2022-03-28 10-second sampling, averaged and logged at 1 minute	
5	2022-03-28 10:00 / 2022-10-05 07:30	Infrared Thermometer; Campbell Scientific; IR120; E1628	Data logger; Campbell Scientific/ CR3000; 1307	1.5/-1/-1	225; Zenith: 85	-	2022-03-28 10-second sampling, averaged and logged at 1 minute	

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-20	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T2920393
2022-03-21	End deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T2920393 Start deployment: Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000031122a6a; Vaisala, CL31, S2010719
2022-03-28	Start deployment: Campbell Scientific, CR3000, 1307; Campbell Scientific, IR120, E1627; Campbell Scientific, IR120, E1628
2022-06-14	End deployment: Vaisala, CL31, S2010719; Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000031122a6a Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T2920393; Raspberry Pi, 4, 10000000845c9e70
2022-10-01	End deployment: All remaining equipment

4.1.19 TUCC (TUB Berlin Campus Charlottenburg)

General site information	
Site name	TUB Campus Charlottenburg
Site code	TUCC
Address	Strasse des 17. Juni 135, D-10623 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.512238
Type of site	13.327804
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	34.06
Station offset (m agl)	45.35
Purpose of site	Inner-city site with comprehensive measurements by TUB, DWL measurements of wakes induced by tall building cluster, IRT measurements
Operator	Technische Universität Berlin; University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site

Looking E (01/08/2022)

Measurement setup

Photographs of instruments

IRT (white tube) with microwave profiler and ALC in background, looking E (01/08/2022)

10 m mast with IRGASON, CNR4, SPN1 at top and Phenocam at bottom (23/05/2023)

CHM15k (28/04/2022)

DWL, looking SE (28/04/2022)

DWL with tall building cluster in background, looking S (28/03/2022)

Comments

Comprehensive further measurements by TUB, including ALC, microwave profiler.

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-03 12:00 / 2022-09-30 08:00	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine XR; 149	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine XR; 149	0/0/0	264	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi	2021-09-03 StreamLine XR v14-6.vi, 12-point VAD scan every 5 minutes at 75° elevation angle, 6-point VAD wind-profile scan every 10 minutes at 75° elevation, rest Stare at 90° elevation angle; 2022-07-28 12-point VAD scan every 30 minutes at 75° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray, every 10 minutes a VAD-6 wind-profile scan at 75° elevation angle for operational purposes, every 25 minutes a PPI (Plan Position Indicator) scan at 0° elevation angle through azimuth angles 96°-210° at 2° resolution, remainder of the time “Stare” at 90° elevation angle with 30,000 pulses/ray.	Instrument potentially has a positive offset
2	2022-06-22 13:00 / 2022-06-28 11:00	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 03	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine; 03	1/0/5	264	StreamLine XR v14-6.vi	StreamLine XR v14-8.vi	Intercomparison with Streamline XR 149; Instrument potentially has a negative offset
3	2022-08-01 10:00 / 2022-10-25 10:27	Infrared Thermometer; Campbell Scientific; IR120; E1632	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16940	1/0/0	195; Zenith: 175	-	2022-08-01 10-second sampling, averaged and logged at 1 minute	

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-20	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T2920393
2022-06-22 / 2022-06-28	Intercomparison of StreamLine XR 149 and StreamLine 03
2022-10-25	End deployment: Campbell Scientific; IR120; E1632

4.1.20 WEDD (Wedding)

General site information	
Site name	Wedding
Site code	WEDD
Address	Müllerstraße 178/S141, D-13353 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.540129
Type of site	13.368945
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	35.75
Station offset (m agl)	65.5
Purpose of site	Inner-city ALC site on perpendicular transect N of city centre, LAS transmitter site
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph(s) of site

23/02/2022

Panorama photographs (30/06/2022)

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (14/10/2022)

Comments	Building heating and ventilation outlet W of instruments with strong ventilation, warm air during cold weather
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Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

BLS2000 transmitter, ClimaVUE50, BLS450 transmitter, and CL61, looking W (23/02/2022)

BLS450 transmitter, ClimaVUE50, BLS2000 transmitter, looking SE (25/10/2021)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-08-26 11:00 / 2022-02-23 08:30	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3320613	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3320613	0/0/0	0	2021-08-26 Firmware v1.0, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 60	2021-08-26 Firmware v1.0, FTP data transfer to server	
2	2022-02-23 09:00 / 2022-10-12 08:00	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL61; T3320613	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000e681c6ea	0/0/0	0	2022-02-23 Firmware v1.0, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 60; 2022-06-30 Firmware v1.1.10, algo.ll averaging.interval = 3, algo.ll averaging.depolinterval = 3, reporting.profile.interval = 3, reporting.livefile.profilesperfile = 20	2022-07-12 FTP data transfer from CL61	
3	2021-10-26 09:15:00/ 2022-10-12 08:00	Weather station; Campbell Scientific; ClimaVUE50; VUE-500002467	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16943	2.5/-3/ -2	0	-	2022-10-26 OS 5.01, 10-second sampling, 1- minute average/sum storage	Potentially issues with wind speed and direction from W due to building; Potentially issues with air temperature and humidity due to building ventilation outlets W of instrument
4	2021-08-26 15:00/ 2022-05-23 07:51	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Transmitter; Scintec; BLS450; T-E-1060	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E- 1051	2/ -2/ -2	123	2021-08-26 boost: OFF, long path: OFF; 2022-01-21 10:00 UTC New LED module installed, boost: OFF, long path: OFF 2022-03-31 09:25 UTC New LED module installed. Old with >10 LED off, boost: OFF, long path: OFF 2022-05-23 Dismounted transmitter with 6 LED off.		BLS450 receiver at MITT; 2022-05-23 Dismounted transmitter for hardware update at manufacturer
5	2021-09-14 13:00/	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS)	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS) Signal	2/ -3/ -2	151	2021-09-14 boost: ON, long path: OFF		BLS2000 receiver at FRIE;

	2022-03-31 09:25	Transmitter; Scintec; BLS2000; T-E-1075	Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1083					2022-03-31 Dismounted transmitter for hardware update at manufacturer
6	2021-10-26 09:15:00/ 2022-10-12 08:00	GPS antenna; Campbell Scientific; GPS16x-HVS; 1A4283814	CR logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16943	0.5/ -2/ -2/	-	-	2021-10-26 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples	Set up for time synchronisation

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-08-26	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL61, T3320613; Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1060
2021-09-14	Start deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1075
2021-10-25	Start deployment: Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002467; Campbell Scientific, CR1000X, 16943
2022-02-23	Start deployment: Raspberry Pi, 4, 10000000e681c6ea
2022-03-31	End deployment: Scintec, BLS2000, T-E-1075
2022-05-23	End deployment: Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1060
2022-10-12	End deployment: All remaining equipment

4.1.21 WEIS (Weissensee)

General site information	
Site name	Weissensee
Site code	WEIS
Address	Goethestrasse 29A, D-13086 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Ground-based
Longitude (° E)	52.55262
Type of site	13.436642
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	48.33
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	ALC site at NE tip of intra-urban grid
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site

11/10/2022

Directional views (04/01/2022)

N

not shown, private property

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (11/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instrument

CL31, looking E (11/10/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-21 11:00 / 2022-10-01 13:50	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL31; S2010717	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 10000000e9d6cbbc	0/0/0	0	2021-09-21 Firmware v3.000, reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = ON		

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-21	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, S2010717; Raspberry Pi, 4, 10000000e9d6cbbc
2022-10-11	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.22 WEST (Westend)

General site information	
Site name	Westend
Site code	WEST
Address	Kolonie Wasserturm, Spandauer Damm 144, D-14050 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Ground-based
Longitude (° E)	52.524105
Type of site	13.269433
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	55.66
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	ALC site at NW tip of intra-urban grid, AWS location
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site

ALC location (14/10/2022)

AWS location (14/10/2022)

Panorama photographs (11/06/2022)

W N E

E S W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (14/10/2022)

ALC location

AWS location

Comment

Site with two sub-locations: ALC location and AWS location, S of ALC location.
Construction and landscape work at both locations, especially AWS location beginning Spring 2022.

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photographs of instrument

CL31 (25/11/2021)

ClimaVUE50 (07/02/2022)

ClimaVUE50 (28/05/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-24 07:00 / 2022-10-02 07:45	Ceilometer; Vaisala; CL31; F2730001	Raspberry Pi; Raspberry Pi Foundation; 4; 1000000b5a683d6	0/0/0	0	2021-09-24 Firmware v3.000, reporting interval 15 s, Message profile noise_h2 = ON		2021-12-19: Detected window blower failure; 2021-12-22: Installed new window blower
2	2021-11-25 10:00 / 2022-10-14 10:00	Weather station; Campbell Scientific; ClimaVUE50; VUE-500002549	CR Logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16936	2/-5/4	0	0	2022-06-23 OS 5.01, 10-second sampling, 1-minute average/sum storage	
3	2021-11-25 10:00 / 2022-10-14 10:00	GPS antenna; Campbell Scientific; GPS16x-HVS; 1A4287558	CR Logger; Campbell Scientific; CR1000X; 16936	0.5/-5/4	-	0	2021-07-15 OS 5.01; 1-hourly samples	Set up for time synchronisation

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-24	Start deployment: Vaisala, CL31, F2730001; Raspberry Pi, 4, 1000000b5a683d6
2021-11-25	Start deployment: Campbell Scientific, CV50, VUE-500002549; Campbell Scientific, CR1000X, 16936
2021-12-19	Detected CL31 window blower failure
2021-12-22	Installed new ALC window blower
2022-10-14	End deployment: All equipment

4.1.23 WILM (Wilmerdorf)

General site information	
Site name	Wilmerdorf
Site code	WILM
Address	Hohenzollerndamm 45-47, D-10713 Berlin
Latitude (° N)	Roof-top
Longitude (° E)	52.489598
Type of site	13.302705
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	45.57
Station offset (m agl)	93.8
Purpose of site	Roof-top DWL site on main transect, SW of city centre, LAS receiver
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site

24/06/2022

Panorama photographs (24/06/2022)

W

N

E

E

S

W

Fisheye photograph/horizon obstruction (01/10/2022)

Measurement setup

Plan view of measurement setup (sketch)

Photograph(s) of instruments

DWL, looking NW (10/10/2022)

BLS450 receiver (10/01/2022)

Measurement configuration								
No.	Time period (start/end) (yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM) (UTC)	Instrument (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Data logger (Type; Manufacturer; Model; Serial number)	Instrument offset (m) (vertical / north / east)	Instrument orientation, Azimuth (degrees)	Instrument firmware; settings; comments	Logger firmware; settings; comments	Comments
1	2021-09-08 09:00 / 2022-10-01 18:17	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine XR; 143	Doppler LiDAR; Halo Photonics; StreamLine XR; 143	1/ 0/ 0	0	2021-09-08 StreamLine XR v14-6.vi; 2021-09-08 Focus = 800 m for all active scan patterns; 2022-07-05 Focus = 2000 m for all active scan patterns	2021-09-08 StreamLine XR v14-6.vi; 2021-09-08 12-point VAD scan every 5 minutes at 75° elevation angle, 6-point VAD wind-profile scan every 10 minutes at 75° elevation, rest Stare at 90° elevation angle; 2022-07-07 Modified scan pattern to daily scan scheduler, 12-point VAD at 75° elevation every 10 minutes, RHI from -2° to 182° elevation at 250° azimuth (continuous) at HH:58:00 until full hour, rest Stare (2000 m focus, 667 gates, 18 m gate length, 3 s/ray); 2022-08-01 11:45 Updated scan schedule with 12-point VAD scan at 75° elevation now every 5 minutes, rest as before	
2	2021-09-08 08:00 / 2022-10-10 07:30	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS); Receiver; Scintec; BLS450/ T-E-1053	Boundary Layer Scintillometer (BLS); Signal Processing Unit (SPU); Scintec; SPU19001; T-E-1050	2/-5/ 3	25	2021-09-08 Dip switches 1 & 5	2021-09-08 SRun-Scin 1.66, continuous mode, 1-minute averages	BLS450 transmitter at CHAR

Event log	
Time period (start/end) (dd/mm/yyyy) (UTC)	Event description
2021-09-08	Start deployment: Halo Photonics, StreamLine XR, 143; Scintec, BLS450, T-E-1053
2022-10-10	End deployment: All equipment

4.2 Partner sites

Details for sites operated by other operators are available at the respective institutions, references are given in Table 16

Table 16: Resources for measurement sites operated by different institutions in the Berlin region.

Operator	Site(s)	Resources
Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)	ANGE, BARU, GENT, KYRI, LIND, MANS, NEUR, POTS, TEMP, WIES, WITT, others	https://www.dwd.de/EN/research/projects/ceilomap/ceilomap_node.html https://www.gruan.org/network/sites/lindenberg https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.669521 https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/photo_db_v3/MetObs_Lindenberg.html https://www.dwd.de/EN/research/observing_atmosphere/lindenberg_column/boundary_layer/boundary_layer_node.html https://cdc.dwd.de/portal/
Freie Universität Berlin (FUB)	FICH, others	https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/photo_db_v3/Berlin_FUB.html https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/met/service/wetterdaten/index.html https://mevis.klimod.de/portal.py https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/en/met/ag/Stadtklima/FUMiNet-OpenStreetMap/index.html
Landesbetrieb Forst Brandenburg (LFB).	KIEN	https://meta.icos-cp.eu/resources/stations/ES_DE-Kie https://www.icos-infrastruktur.de/icos-d/komponenten/oekosysteme/beobachtungsstandorte/kienhorst-assoziert
HTW Berlin, University of Applied Sciences (HTW)	OSWE	https://wetter.htw-berlin.de/
Technische Universität Berlin (TUB)	FOGR, ROTH, TUCC, others	https://uco.berlin/en https://meta.icos-cp.eu/resources/stations/ES_DE-BeR

4.3 Temporary sites

Three additional temporary sites were operated during the IOP in Summer 2022 by *urbisphere* to conduct mobile ALC measurements and for radiosonde launches.

4.3.1 GLEI (Gleisdreieck)

General site information	
Site name	Gleisdreieck
Site code	GLEI
Latitude (° N)	52.494010
Longitude (° E)	13.376607
Type of site	Ground-based
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	37.5
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	Inner-city launch site for radiosondes on 04/08/2022 and 11/08/2022
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photographs of site (11/08/2022)

4.3.2 RAGO (Ragow)

General site information	
Site name	Ragow
Site code	RAGO
Latitude (° N)	52.296605
Longitude (° E)	13.538686
Type of site	Ground-based
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	44.1
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	Rural launch site for radiosondes on 11/08/2022 and turn-around point of mobile ALC tour
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photograph of site (11/08/2022)

4.3.3 ZOSS (Zossen)

General site information	
Site name	Zossen
Site code	ZOSS
Latitude (° N)	52.232072
Longitude (° E)	13.357386
Type of site	Ground-based
Elevation, ground (m amsl)	49.3
Station offset (m agl)	-
Purpose of site	Rural launch site for radiosondes and stationary ALC measurements on 04/08/2022
Operator	University of Freiburg

Microscale map (100 x 100 m²)

Photographs of site (04/08/2022)

Stationary ALC in van, looking SW

Stationary ALC in van, looking NE

Looking NE

Looking E

Appendix

A.1 Daily weather conditions

Table A1: Daily information for the urbisphere-Berlin campaign period (01/10/2021-30/09/2022), including relevant weather conditions. DOY: Day of year, UTC: Universal Time Coordinated, DOW: Day of week, IOP: Intensive Observation Period, T_{mean} : Daily mean air temperature, T_{max} : Daily maximum air temperature, T_{min} : Daily minimum air temperature, VP: Daily mean vapour pressure, P: Daily mean station air pressure, PRCP: Daily precipitation sum, Thunders.: Daily number of thunderstorms, SH: Snow height, Sun: Daily sum of sunshine hours, CCF: Daily mean cloud-cover fraction, WS_{mean} : Daily mean wind speed (scalar), WS_{max} : Daily maximum wind speed, WD_{mean} : Daily mean wind direction (vector), Heat warning: Daily heat warning by Deutscher Wetterdienst. Sunset and sunrise are calculated for city-centre site FRIE. Public holidays, school holidays, and heat warnings refer to Berlin administrative area. Colour codes detailed in Table A.2 below this table. Data sources: Berlin-Tempelhof (DWD ID 433, DWD 2023a) for all weather variables except: Thunders., SH, Sun, CCF, which are from Berlin-Dahlem FU (DWD ID 403, DWD 2023a, 2023b).

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2021-10-01	274	05:08:39	16:45:56	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	12.7	18.9	7.0	9.0	1015.3	0.0	0	0	10.2	6.0	3.1	8.9	153.9	0
2021-10-02	275	05:10:21	16:43:35	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	14.8	20.2	9.7	11.6	1007.2	0.0	0	0	7.5	6.4	2.8	8.1	167.1	0
2021-10-03	276	05:12:03	16:41:14	Sun	1	1	0	0	0	18.1	24.7	13.9	12.3	1002.6	0.2	0	0	3.1	6.8	3.7	10.6	151.3	0
2021-10-04	277	05:13:45	16:38:53	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	14.8	17.8	13.3	13.0	1011.6	0.3	0	0	0.0	7.3	2.2	7.5	265.9	0
2021-10-05	278	05:15:28	16:36:33	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	13.1	14.8	11.2	13.5	1005.0	5.1	0	0	0.0	7.5	2.7	6.9	133.5	0
2021-10-06	279	05:17:11	16:34:13	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	13.2	16.2	7.7	11.8	1011.0	0.0	0	0	5.2	4.2	2.5	6.8	199.4	0
2021-10-07	280	05:18:54	16:31:54	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	12.0	19.0	5.1	10.7	1022.4	0.1	0	0	10.6	1.5	1.2	4.4	31.8	0
2021-10-08	281	05:20:38	16:29:35	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	11.9	16.7	6.1	10.1	1026.5	0.0	0	0	9.6	1.4	3.2	7.4	74.4	0
2021-10-09	282	05:22:22	16:27:17	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	9.2	15.5	4.1	7.1	1027.4	0.0	0	0	10.4	0.5	3.5	8.9	96.0	0
2021-10-10	283	05:24:06	16:25:00	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	8.0	15.0	1.4	6.6	1022.7	0.0	0	0	9.9	1.0	2.2	7.5	127.0	0
2021-10-11	284	05:25:51	16:22:43	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	8.8	14.4	2.6	9.1	1015.2	1.4	0	0	4.8	4.5	3.0	9.8	265.3	0
2021-10-12	285	05:27:36	16:20:27	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	9.1	13.2	5.3	8.6	1009.4	0.0	0	0	4.7	4.3	4.9	12.6	294.4	0
2021-10-13	286	05:29:22	16:18:12	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	8.2	12.5	4.1	8.1	1014.9	1.4	0	0	7.3	4.0	3.6	8.2	275.5	0
2021-10-14	287	05:31:07	16:15:57	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	11.0	13.1	8.6	11.8	1013.7	1.8	0	0	0.0	7.6	3.3	7.4	238.8	0
2021-10-15	288	05:32:54	16:13:44	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	10.9	13.6	7.2	10.7	1008.5	1.7	0	0	1.7	5.0	4.5	12.7	238.9	0
2021-10-16	289	05:34:40	16:11:31	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	9.3	13.0	5.9	9.3	1014.9	0.8	0	0	3.3	5.8	2.8	7.0	254.9	0
2021-10-17	290	05:36:27	16:09:19	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	10.0	12.5	6.7	9.3	1014.5	1.1	0	0	1.1	6.8	2.9	8.6	244.1	0
2021-10-18	291	05:38:15	16:07:08	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	11.9	16.3	9.2	9.8	1017.6	0.0	0	0	4.2	7.0	2.3	7.3	223.8	0
2021-10-19	292	05:40:02	16:04:59	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	12.8	16.7	8.4	11.6	1012.8	0.1	0	0	2.5	7.2	3.1	8.9	200.9	0
2021-10-20	293	05:41:50	16:02:50	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	16.0	19.5	13.1	13.2	1000.6	1.2	0	0	1.8	6.6	4.7	11.8	208.1	0
2021-10-21	294	05:43:39	16:00:42	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	13.0	17.4	7.0	10.6	991.0	1.4	0	0	1.2	6.2	7.5	22.5	237.8	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T _{mean} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T _{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS _{mean} (m/s)	WS _{max} (m/s)	WD _{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2021-10-22	295	05:45:27	15:58:35	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	7.5	10.5	6.0	7.9	1003.8	3.7	0	0	0.0	5.2	6.4	16.7	247.4	0
2021-10-23	296	05:47:16	15:56:30	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	7.6	11.5	4.6	8.0	1018.3	0.0	0	0	7.2	3.0	4.6	12.3	270.0	0
2021-10-24	297	05:49:06	15:54:25	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	7.6	12.7	3.3	7.7	1022.3	0.0	0	0	9.5	3.5	2.3	8.1	153.3	0
2021-10-25	298	05:50:55	15:52:22	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	6.7	11.1	1.9	7.5	1014.6	0.0	0	0	5.8	4.3	2.2	7.2	179.7	0
2021-10-26	299	05:52:45	15:50:20	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	9.9	14.1	4.6	10.1	1013.9	0.0	0	0	0.5	6.9	2.3	7.8	222.4	0
2021-10-27	300	05:54:35	15:48:20	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	12.5	14.2	10.2	11.3	1016.9	0.0	0	0	1.2	7.6	3.3	7.5	211.6	0
2021-10-28	301	05:56:26	15:46:21	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	11.3	16.7	7.1	10.2	1014.8	0.0	0	0	9.1	1.9	2.5	6.8	150.4	0
2021-10-29	302	05:58:16	15:44:23	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	9.2	14.9	4.2	8.7	1008.2	0.0	0	0	9.0	1.3	2.4	6.1	149.8	0
2021-10-30	303	06:00:07	15:42:26	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	10.3	15.2	5.1	8.3	1003.7	0.0	0	0	8.2	4.6	2.7	8.2	150.2	0
2021-10-31	304	06:01:58	15:40:31	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	13.4	18.2	10.2	10.2	1002.5	0.0	0	0	8.0	4.5	3.1	9.2	155.4	0
2021-11-01	305	06:03:49	15:38:38	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	10.4	12.7	8.1	10.2	996.8	1.2	0	0	0.0	6.0	2.8	7.4	173.1	0
2021-11-02	306	06:05:40	15:36:46	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	9.5	11.8	6.4	10.4	995.4	0.0	0	0	0.9	7.0	1.9	4.6	177.9	0
2021-11-03	307	06:07:31	15:34:56	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	7.1	12.0	2.2	8.6	997.6	0.0	0	0	1.7	5.0	2.0	5.4	111.3	0
2021-11-04	308	06:09:22	15:33:08	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	7.0	8.9	6.2	9.2	993.0	38.6	0	0	0.0	7.9	5.2	17.9	311.1	0
2021-11-05	309	06:11:14	15:31:21	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	8.3	9.9	6.5	9.4	1010.8	0.0	0	0	0.0	6.9	4.8	10.6	263.5	0
2021-11-06	310	06:13:05	15:29:36	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	9.2	11.7	6.9	9.0	1017.9	0.0	0	0	0.7	6.9	4.4	10.1	229.3	0
2021-11-07	311	06:14:55	15:27:53	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	8.4	10.8	7.1	8.8	1005.8	6.1	0	0	0.5	6.2	5.2	13.4	230.1	0
2021-11-08	312	06:16:46	15:26:11	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	8.8	10.9	7.2	9.5	1012.8	0.7	0	0	0.3	7.2	4.2	10.0	263.9	0
2021-11-09	313	06:18:37	15:24:32	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	8.5	11.7	4.4	9.5	1022.1	0.0	0	0	2.5	4.7	2.2	5.1	197.7	0
2021-11-10	314	06:20:27	15:22:54	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	5.2	9.1	0.3	7.4	1019.7	0.0	0	0	8.0	4.2	1.5	5.8	176.9	0
2021-11-11	315	06:22:17	15:21:19	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	5.6	9.7	0.1	8.2	1017.9	0.2	0	0	5.6	5.5	1.7	5.7	229.0	0
2021-11-12	316	06:24:06	15:19:46	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	7.0	8.5	3.0	9.1	1014.4	0.0	0	0	0.0	6.3	2.8	9.2	147.5	0
2021-11-13	317	06:25:55	15:18:14	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	4.9	8.8	2.8	7.5	1009.4	0.0	0	0	3.1	6.8	2.1	6.9	148.4	0
2021-11-14	318	06:27:44	15:16:45	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	6.1	7.3	5.0	8.1	1018.6	0.0	0	0	0.2	7.7	2.7	9.1	60.9	0
2021-11-15	319	06:29:32	15:15:19	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	5.6	6.0	5.3	7.6	1023.0	0.0	0	0	0.0	8.0	3.5	7.5	82.4	0
2021-11-16	320	06:31:19	15:13:54	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	6.2	7.9	4.9	8.1	1017.6	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.9	2.9	6.7	120.4	0
2021-11-17	321	06:33:05	15:12:32	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	5.8	7.7	4.4	7.8	1013.5	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.6	3.5	8.9	237.9	0
2021-11-18	322	06:34:51	15:11:12	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	8.1	10.2	6.0	9.2	1017.0	3.1	0	0	0.0	6.9	4.6	11.1	249.0	0
2021-11-19	323	06:36:36	15:09:55	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	11.6	12.7	9.7	11.4	1016.6	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.8	5.9	12.2	267.5	0
2021-11-20	324	06:38:20	15:08:40	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	11.1	11.9	9.8	10.7	1013.9	0.0	0	0	0.2	7.8	5.2	10.6	259.1	0
2021-11-21	325	06:40:03	15:07:28	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	8.0	9.9	3.6	9.2	1004.2	1.4	0	0	0.0	7.3	3.3	9.0	253.6	0
2021-11-22	326	06:41:44	15:06:18	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	3.9	6.6	0.6	6.4	1016.5	0.2	0	0	5.8	3.0	3.8	8.5	334.9	0
2021-11-23	327	06:43:25	15:05:11	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	5.0	7.1	0.4	8.2	1019.9	1.4	0	0	0.0	7.0	3.5	7.8	254.1	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2021-11-24	328	06:45:04	15:04:07	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	6.9	7.8	5.9	9.0	1015.9	0.3	0	0	0.2	7.7	2.6	5.9	243.5	0
2021-11-25	329	06:46:42	15:03:05	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	4.5	5.9	3.4	6.5	1003.3	0.0	0	0	0.6	7.5	3.1	7.9	211.3	0
2021-11-26	330	06:48:18	15:02:07	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	4.4	6.2	2.1	6.3	992.6	0.0	0	0	2.5	6.8	3.0	7.9	194.4	0
2021-11-27	331	06:49:53	15:01:11	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	1.9	3.6	0.5	5.9	986.8	4.9	0	0	0.8	6.6	2.7	7.4	147.2	0
2021-11-28	332	06:51:26	15:00:19	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	1.9	5.2	-0.2	6.2	990.7	1.2	0	0	7.1	4.9	1.8	5.5	195.7	0
2021-11-29	333	06:52:57	14:59:29	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	2.4	3.6	1.6	6.5	996.6	1.1	0	0	0.4	7.5	3.7	8.8	291.6	0
2021-11-30	334	06:54:27	14:58:42	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	3.4	6.2	1.1	6.5	993.5	7.1	0	0	0.0	6.8	6.3	20.4	265.9	0
2021-12-01	335	06:55:55	14:57:59	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	5.9	8.9	2.3	7.7	986.8	4.3	0	0	0.0	7.5	4.9	18.9	214.1	0
2021-12-02	336	06:57:20	14:57:18	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	2.3	6.1	-1.5	5.0	990.5	0.0	0	0	6.5	2.5	7.0	21.3	273.2	0
2021-12-03	337	06:58:44	14:56:41	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	1.0	3.9	-2.0	5.0	1001.0	0.7	0	0	4.0	5.3	4.5	11.0	223.5	0
2021-12-04	338	07:00:05	14:56:07	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	1.5	2.3	0.5	6.1	994.5	2.9	0	0	0.0	8.0	3.4	8.4	154.3	0
2021-12-05	339	07:01:24	14:55:37	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	0.7	1.2	0.3	6.0	998.7	0.3	0	1	0.0	8.0	2.1	6.4	62.5	0
2021-12-06	340	07:02:41	14:55:09	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	0.8	2.0	-0.3	5.7	1008.8	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.5	2.4	6.6	64.1	0
2021-12-07	341	07:03:55	14:54:45	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	-0.4	0.2	-1.6	5.2	1006.0	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.4	3.9	8.4	119.1	0
2021-12-08	342	07:05:07	14:54:25	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	-0.1	1.2	-1.0	5.0	1000.1	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.6	5.1	10.6	117.2	0
2021-12-09	343	07:06:16	14:54:08	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	-1.1	-0.7	-1.7	5.0	1000.0	2.9	0	0	0.0	8.0	2.6	7.3	108.2	0
2021-12-10	344	07:07:23	14:53:54	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	-0.2	0.6	-1.2	5.7	994.6	1.5	0	4	0.0	7.9	1.9	5.4	123.9	0
2021-12-11	345	07:08:26	14:53:44	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	-0.7	-0.1	-1.9	5.5	1007.8	0.0	0	2	0.0	8.0	1.9	5.2	203.7	0
2021-12-12	346	07:09:27	14:53:37	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	1.0	5.3	-1.8	6.1	1016.8	0.3	0	1	0.0	7.3	2.3	5.9	200.5	0
2021-12-13	347	07:10:25	14:53:34	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	7.1	9.4	5.2	9.8	1019.7	1.9	0	0	0.0	8.0	1.9	5.4	231.0	0
2021-12-14	348	07:11:20	14:53:35	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	7.5	8.4	7.0	9.4	1020.0	0.6	0	0	0.0	7.8	2.7	6.5	241.3	0
2021-12-15	349	07:12:12	14:53:39	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	8.7	9.9	7.7	10.0	1022.8	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.8	3.1	8.0	244.4	0
2021-12-16	350	07:13:01	14:53:46	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	9.5	5.4	9.1	1027.2	0.1	0	0	2.1	5.7	4.6	9.6	290.1	0
2021-12-17	351	07:13:46	14:53:57	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	5.4	6.1	4.7	7.6	1030.8	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.2	5.0	9.9	315.8	0
2021-12-18	352	07:14:29	14:54:12	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	6.0	7.8	4.8	8.5	1027.3	0.2	0	0	0.0	7.9	4.3	11.9	286.5	0
2021-12-19	353	07:15:08	14:54:30	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	6.0	7.3	1.5	8.1	1015.6	6.2	0	0	0.0	6.3	6.9	14.4	302.3	0
2021-12-20	354	07:15:44	14:54:52	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	1.4	3.1	-0.7	5.7	1018.5	0.1	0	0	4.1	2.9	3.8	9.6	306.4	0
2021-12-21	355	07:16:16	14:55:17	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	0.7	1.4	-0.5	5.7	1020.5	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.8	2.2	5.0	294.6	0
2021-12-22	356	07:16:45	14:55:45	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	-0.5	1.6	-3.1	4.7	1020.6	0.0	0	0	6.5	5.7	2.1	6.9	209.0	0
2021-12-23	357	07:17:11	14:56:18	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	-1.1	1.2	-3.6	4.8	1005.2	7.6	0	0	0.0	7.6	2.7	7.1	181.1	0
2021-12-24	358	07:17:33	14:56:53	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	2.0	5.8	-5.3	6.6	994.3	5.8	0	0	0.0	7.5	4.4	11.8	309.7	0
2021-12-25	359	07:17:52	14:57:32	Sat	1	1	1	0	0	-5.5	0.1	-8.9	3.2	1007.4	0.0	0	0	7.5	1.0	1.2	5.4	295.3	0
2021-12-26	360	07:18:07	14:58:14	Sun	1	1	1	0	0	-6.8	-1.9	-10.8	2.8	1008.6	0.0	0	0	7.4	0.0	2.4	6.8	104.3	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2021-12-27	361	07:18:19	14:59:00	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	-3.9	-0.9	-8.3	3.5	1002.3	0.0	0	0	0.2	5.9	3.9	7.5	112.8	0
2021-12-28	362	07:18:27	14:59:49	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	-0.5	2.9	-4.3	5.0	994.3	1.5	0	0	0.0	6.4	3.7	7.2	119.9	0
2021-12-29	363	07:18:32	15:00:41	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	4.5	5.9	2.4	8.1	998.3	0.1	0	0	0.0	7.5	2.0	6.3	224.4	0
2021-12-30	364	07:18:33	15:01:36	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	9.3	12.9	4.6	11.3	1005.6	2.8	0	0	0.0	7.9	3.7	10.9	240.1	0
2021-12-31	365	07:18:31	15:02:34	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	13.0	14.2	11.8	12.7	1008.6	5.6	0	0	0.0	7.7	5.4	13.8	250.3	0
2022-01-01	1	07:18:25	15:03:36	Sat	1	1	1	0	0	12.0	12.7	9.9	12.2	1015.6	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.3	4.0	10.0	253.6	0
2022-01-02	2	07:18:16	15:04:40	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	9.9	11.7	7.9	10.3	1006.6	3.8	0	0	0.0	6.6	3.8	11.0	213.8	0
2022-01-03	3	07:18:03	15:05:47	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	8.9	10.8	6.2	9.1	1000.3	0.7	0	0	0.6	5.5	4.9	17.9	238.4	0
2022-01-04	4	07:17:47	15:06:57	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	6.4	7.2	4.1	8.6	990.6	1.7	0	0	0.0	7.4	3.0	9.1	231.1	0
2022-01-05	5	07:17:28	15:08:09	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	3.8	5.1	2.5	6.5	992.2	1.0	0	0	1.3	6.9	4.6	12.9	240.4	0
2022-01-06	6	07:17:05	15:09:24	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	1.2	3.9	-1.4	4.9	1008.0	0.0	0	0	7.4	1.4	4.7	14.1	288.7	0
2022-01-07	7	07:16:39	15:10:42	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	0.7	2.9	-1.5	5.5	1007.8	1.4	0	0	0.4	6.1	3.6	10.0	195.7	0
2022-01-08	8	07:16:09	15:12:02	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	1.3	3.3	-0.6	5.9	1002.3	0.0	0	1	2.1	5.9	2.8	8.1	193.4	0
2022-01-09	9	07:15:36	15:13:25	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	1.5	4.3	-0.9	5.5	993.5	0.1	0	0	0.0	6.9	3.6	9.4	149.3	0
2022-01-10	10	07:15:00	15:14:50	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	3.1	5.1	-2.4	6.9	1014.3	0.1	0	0	0.0	7.0	2.4	5.9	49.3	0
2022-01-11	11	07:14:21	15:16:17	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	-2.3	-0.1	-3.4	4.5	1029.4	0.0	0	0	1.3	6.6	2.5	7.0	158.7	0
2022-01-12	12	07:13:38	15:17:46	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	0.9	3.7	-2.4	6.0	1030.3	0.3	0	0	0.0	7.8	2.8	7.7	252.6	0
2022-01-13	13	07:12:53	15:19:17	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	4.3	5.2	3.5	7.3	1028.0	0.0	0	0	0.0	8.0	5.1	11.0	266.1	0
2022-01-14	14	07:12:04	15:20:50	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	5.3	6.8	2.4	7.8	1023.2	0.3	0	0	0.0	7.1	5.4	12.3	280.4	0
2022-01-15	15	07:11:13	15:22:25	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	1.9	3.3	0.6	6.0	1022.8	0.0	0	0	0.2	6.2	2.4	6.3	273.3	0
2022-01-16	16	07:10:18	15:24:02	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	2.1	5.5	-1.0	6.2	1014.3	0.5	0	0	0.0	7.4	3.6	12.7	242.3	0
2022-01-17	17	07:09:21	15:25:40	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	4.1	6.2	0.4	6.5	1015.8	4.9	0	0	1.4	4.6	7.2	20.1	290.1	0
2022-01-18	18	07:08:21	15:27:20	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	3.0	5.5	-0.8	6.4	1028.4	0.0	0	0	0.1	5.8	3.1	8.3	277.4	0
2022-01-19	19	07:07:18	15:29:02	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	4.0	5.2	2.4	6.6	1016.1	0.7	0	0	2.5	7.8	4.3	16.1	239.1	0
2022-01-20	20	07:06:12	15:30:44	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	1.1	4.0	-2.4	4.9	1009.2	0.5	0	1	2.6	5.0	7.6	22.2	291.9	0
2022-01-21	21	07:05:03	15:32:29	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	3.4	-2.9	4.4	1017.6	2.2	0	4	8.2	3.2	5.7	11.8	284.6	0
2022-01-22	22	07:03:52	15:34:14	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	3.0	4.4	1.3	6.4	1021.0	0.6	0	0	1.7	6.8	3.4	10.1	313.3	0
2022-01-23	23	07:02:38	15:36:00	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	5.4	6.7	4.4	8.4	1026.2	0.8	0	0	0.0	7.6	3.2	6.9	301.0	0
2022-01-24	24	07:01:22	15:37:48	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	5.3	6.6	4.2	8.2	1028.1	0.2	0	0	0.5	7.7	2.7	7.1	293.6	0
2022-01-25	25	07:00:04	15:39:36	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	4.0	4.6	3.0	7.4	1025.3	1.4	0	0	0.0	7.9	3.8	7.5	281.3	0
2022-01-26	26	06:58:42	15:41:26	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	2.9	4.0	1.8	6.7	1021.1	0.3	0	0	0.0	7.9	4.7	11.0	264.0	0
2022-01-27	27	06:57:19	15:43:16	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	4.4	6.3	3.0	7.0	1009.8	0.8	0	0	0.0	7.5	6.3	18.4	252.4	0
2022-01-28	28	06:55:53	15:45:07	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	4.9	6.5	3.3	6.0	1016.8	1.2	0	0	5.4	6.5	7.8	18.5	293.0	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-01-29	29	06:54:25	15:46:58	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	5.8	9.6	2.7	7.8	1009.0	5.7	0	0	0.0	7.4	6.8	26.0	254.0	0
2022-01-30	30	06:52:55	15:48:50	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	5.8	6.9	4.1	5.7	1007.0	0.0	0	0	0.4	7.1	10.6	24.9	288.9	0
2022-01-31	31	06:51:23	15:50:43	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	2.9	4.7	-0.1	5.5	1001.6	0.4	0	0	0.0	7.1	3.0	11.8	278.8	0
2022-02-01	32	06:49:48	15:52:36	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	3.4	6.5	1.3	6.7	999.7	4.4	0	0	0.0	7.3	6.4	19.4	262.7	0
2022-02-02	33	06:48:12	15:54:30	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	4.9	6.7	1.5	6.4	1002.4	0.1	0	0	1.5	5.9	8.3	22.4	295.9	0
2022-02-03	34	06:46:34	15:56:24	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	4.5	6.8	1.4	7.7	1009.6	4.1	0	0	0.1	7.0	3.7	11.7	208.5	0
2022-02-04	35	06:44:53	15:58:18	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	6.6	8.2	3.2	8.1	1001.8	0.8	0	0	0.0	8.0	7.6	23.7	207.2	0
2022-02-05	36	06:43:11	16:00:13	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	4.5	6.4	1.3	6.2	1007.3	3.5	0	0	1.2	7.3	7.6	14.2	237.9	0
2022-02-06	37	06:41:27	16:02:07	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	5.4	7.7	4.0	7.4	993.9	8.0	0	0	0.1	7.8	8.8	18.1	217.7	0
2022-02-07	38	06:39:41	16:04:02	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	3.9	6.8	2.1	6.1	1004.1	0.2	0	0	2.1	5.8	9.1	18.5	274.0	0
2022-02-08	39	06:37:54	16:05:57	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	6.2	9.2	2.7	8.4	1015.8	1.4	0	0	0.0	7.5	6.8	13.8	234.6	0
2022-02-09	40	06:36:05	16:07:52	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	9.0	10.0	8.4	9.4	1016.6	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.7	6.5	12.7	227.3	0
2022-02-10	41	06:34:14	16:09:47	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	7.5	10.5	3.1	8.3	1012.3	0.8	0	0	0.1	7.7	5.0	14.1	227.8	0
2022-02-11	42	06:32:22	16:11:42	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	3.8	6.1	0.2	6.6	1016.6	0.1	0	0	2.1	5.5	4.8	12.1	245.2	0
2022-02-12	43	06:30:28	16:13:37	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	1.1	5.4	-2.7	5.0	1024.7	0.0	0	0	8.5	2.0	4.5	11.6	187.9	0
2022-02-13	44	06:28:32	16:15:31	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	3.5	8.0	-0.8	5.4	1010.8	0.0	0	0	9.2	5.3	4.9	12.7	179.8	0
2022-02-14	45	06:26:35	16:17:26	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	7.9	13.8	2.9	5.9	1000.6	0.0	0	0	7.5	5.9	5.7	14.5	178.2	0
2022-02-15	46	06:24:37	16:19:20	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	7.4	10.6	5.0	7.2	1003.2	1.0	0	0	2.3	5.7	4.3	10.3	209.7	0
2022-02-16	47	06:22:37	16:21:15	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	7.5	12.9	4.7	8.6	991.5	8.6	0	0	0.0	7.6	6.1	19.7	209.1	0
2022-02-17	48	06:20:37	16:23:09	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	8.1	13.0	5.0	7.5	986.3	1.2	1	0	2.1	5.4	10.5	25.9	270.4	0
2022-02-18	49	06:18:34	16:25:03	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	6.8	10.9	4.0	7.3	994.2	3.5	0	0	1.4	5.0	6.3	27.9	232.9	0
2022-02-19	50	06:16:31	16:26:56	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	6.1	8.3	3.5	5.4	999.0	3.2	0	0	1.3	6.6	8.8	27.0	250.1	0
2022-02-20	51	06:14:26	16:28:49	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	5.5	9.0	2.2	7.9	997.6	6.5	0	0	0.5	7.9	5.3	14.8	222.3	0
2022-02-21	52	06:12:21	16:30:42	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	5.7	10.5	3.2	7.0	988.1	3.4	0	0	0.7	6.9	7.4	21.6	251.8	0
2022-02-22	53	06:10:14	16:32:35	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	5.8	8.2	4.1	6.8	1004.1	1.7	0	0	3.8	6.6	6.3	15.3	266.5	0
2022-02-23	54	06:08:06	16:34:28	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	6.5	10.3	2.4	6.7	1013.9	0.0	0	0	7.3	3.3	5.8	16.2	270.2	0
2022-02-24	55	06:05:57	16:36:20	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	5.9	10.3	1.2	6.5	1006.0	0.3	0	0	1.8	5.1	4.3	18.3	209.0	0
2022-02-25	56	06:03:47	16:38:11	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	4.4	7.5	2.1	6.1	1010.6	2.2	0	0	3.3	5.8	5.5	14.1	244.9	0
2022-02-26	57	06:01:36	16:40:03	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	4.1	6.7	-0.2	6.3	1025.6	0.0	0	0	0.4	5.5	3.8	8.9	333.0	0
2022-02-27	58	05:59:24	16:41:54	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	0.5	4.4	-1.9	5.8	1031.6	0.0	0	0	8.4	3.2	2.4	5.7	88.8	0
2022-02-28	59	05:57:12	16:43:45	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	1.7	6.0	-0.9	4.9	1030.6	0.0	0	0	8.2	3.2	2.6	7.1	116.2	0
2022-03-01	60	05:54:58	16:45:35	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	2.1	7.8	-2.5	3.7	1026.8	0.0	0	0	9.6	1.7	2.9	7.3	146.0	0
2022-03-02	61	05:52:44	16:47:25	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	2.1	9.0	-3.0	4.1	1020.1	0.0	0	0	8.4	4.0	1.3	4.3	84.0	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-03-03	62	05:50:29	16:49:15	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	-0.4	2.3	-3.6	4.9	1016.0	0.0	0	0	1.8	4.6	2.5	6.7	13.3	0
2022-03-04	63	05:48:14	16:51:04	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	1.8	4.4	-0.6	5.2	1018.3	0.0	0	0	0.2	6.9	2.7	7.3	32.7	0
2022-03-05	64	05:45:57	16:52:53	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	0.8	6.0	-2.3	4.6	1019.2	0.0	0	0	6.6	2.2	2.1	6.7	56.9	0
2022-03-06	65	05:43:40	16:54:42	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	0.9	2.2	-0.4	4.0	1019.6	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.5	2.9	7.1	4.3	0
2022-03-07	66	05:41:23	16:56:30	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	3.2	9.0	-2.5	4.8	1019.9	0.0	0	0	10.7	1.5	3.5	9.6	342.2	0
2022-03-08	67	05:39:04	16:58:18	Tue	0	1	0	0	0	3.8	11.2	-2.8	5.0	1020.1	0.0	0	0	10.9	0.7	1.0	3.8	345.7	0
2022-03-09	68	05:36:46	17:00:06	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	5.0	12.1	-2.5	5.1	1020.6	0.0	0	0	11.0	0.0	1.5	6.0	57.7	0
2022-03-10	69	05:34:27	17:01:54	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	4.1	9.3	-0.6	4.8	1025.0	0.0	0	0	10.0	0.7	3.9	10.3	111.0	0
2022-03-11	70	05:32:07	17:03:41	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	3.0	8.6	-2.2	2.7	1023.4	0.0	0	0	11.1	0.3	5.7	12.7	117.8	0
2022-03-12	71	05:29:47	17:05:28	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	4.8	12.0	-2.1	2.7	1019.7	0.0	0	0	11.2	0.4	4.4	9.9	123.2	0
2022-03-13	72	05:27:26	17:07:14	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	6.6	13.3	-1.2	2.9	1016.8	0.0	0	0	11.3	0.0	4.3	9.9	115.2	0
2022-03-14	73	05:25:06	17:09:01	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	13.7	1.8	5.0	1019.3	1.3	0	0	7.9	3.7	3.6	8.6	172.0	0
2022-03-15	74	05:22:44	17:10:47	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	8.5	12.6	2.5	8.4	1021.0	0.0	0	0	4.8	6.1	2.0	5.2	170.1	0
2022-03-16	75	05:20:23	17:12:33	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	6.5	11.3	3.1	7.9	1022.2	0.0	0	0	11.0	3.7	3.1	7.1	59.6	0
2022-03-17	76	05:18:01	17:14:19	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	7.7	11.9	4.0	7.6	1024.3	0.0	0	0	0.0	7.8	3.4	8.9	116.7	0
2022-03-18	77	05:15:39	17:16:04	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	8.6	13.3	5.5	6.7	1035.8	0.0	0	0	10.8	4.0	3.8	8.8	9.2	0
2022-03-19	78	05:13:17	17:17:49	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	6.3	10.9	1.0	5.8	1037.5	0.0	0	0	9.9	0.8	5.2	12.9	58.3	0
2022-03-20	79	05:10:55	17:19:35	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	6.6	12.7	0.4	3.6	1033.1	0.0	0	0	11.3	0.0	5.3	13.9	108.3	0
2022-03-21	80	05:08:33	17:21:20	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	14.1	0.9	3.5	1030.6	0.0	0	0	11.4	0.5	3.7	11.2	131.0	0
2022-03-22	81	05:06:10	17:23:04	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	8.8	17.5	1.0	3.7	1028.5	0.0	0	0	11.8	0.0	2.3	7.4	132.9	0
2022-03-23	82	05:03:48	17:24:49	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	9.9	19.6	0.7	4.8	1024.8	0.0	0	0	11.5	0.0	2.1	7.5	32.9	0
2022-03-24	83	05:01:26	17:26:34	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	8.6	16.5	0.7	4.9	1023.6	0.0	0	0	11.6	0.1	1.6	4.3	32.5	0
2022-03-25	84	04:59:03	17:28:18	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	10.0	17.3	1.7	6.6	1023.1	0.0	0	0	10.0	0.7	2.1	7.9	307.3	0
2022-03-26	85	04:56:41	17:30:03	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	9.4	13.9	5.0	8.5	1022.8	0.0	0	0	4.3	4.6	4.3	10.9	308.2	0
2022-03-27	86	04:54:18	17:31:47	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	9.7	16.4	1.6	7.9	1024.1	0.0	0	0	11.6	1.6	1.8	7.2	261.9	0
2022-03-28	87	04:51:56	17:33:32	Mon	0	0	0	0	1	10.8	17.2	5.3	7.8	1014.0	0.0	0	0	11.9	1.0	4.2	11.0	281.1	0
2022-03-29	88	04:49:34	17:35:16	Tue	0	0	0	0	1	8.0	12.9	3.6	6.1	1004.4	0.0	0	0	6.9	4.9	4.9	11.5	297.3	0
2022-03-30	89	04:47:13	17:37:00	Wed	0	0	0	0	1	5.3	9.2	1.4	5.0	999.6	0.0	0	0	1.5	6.9	3.0	10.0	51.7	0
2022-03-31	90	04:44:51	17:38:44	Thu	0	0	0	0	1	3.8	7.3	-1.0	3.8	998.5	0.0	0	0	6.1	7.0	6.8	17.8	79.9	0
2022-04-01	91	04:42:30	17:40:29	Fri	0	0	0	0	1	3.7	7.6	0.3	3.3	1000.5	0.0	0	0	6.9	7.5	7.9	16.2	42.1	0
2022-04-02	92	04:40:09	17:42:13	Sat	1	0	0	0	1	2.1	6.5	-2.2	4.1	1008.1	0.0	0	0	2.0	5.6	6.3	14.0	16.3	0
2022-04-03	93	04:37:48	17:43:57	Sun	1	0	0	Half marathon	1	2.8	8.0	-3.9	4.4	1011.7	0.1	0	0	5.8	6.2	4.0	12.9	279.2	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-04-04	94	04:35:28	17:45:41	Mon	0	0	0	0	1	3.9	8.1	1.0	6.1	1000.0	9.7	0	0	2.3	7.5	6.4	17.4	228.1	0
2022-04-05	95	04:33:08	17:47:26	Tue	0	0	0	0	1	7.0	9.1	4.8	7.8	995.1	3.4	0	0	2.4	7.4	5.0	14.6	270.4	0
2022-04-06	96	04:30:48	17:49:10	Wed	0	0	0	0	1	10.5	12.5	8.8	9.2	993.4	0.1	0	0	0.5	7.8	4.7	13.2	232.0	0
2022-04-07	97	04:28:29	17:50:54	Thu	0	0	0	0	1	10.2	14.5	6.2	8.6	981.3	8.5	0	0	3.5	6.3	6.0	19.3	219.4	0
2022-04-08	98	04:26:11	17:52:39	Fri	0	0	0	0	1	7.0	9.4	2.8	6.6	987.6	0.8	0	0	2.6	6.8	6.0	18.8	262.2	0
2022-04-09	99	04:23:53	17:54:23	Sat	1	0	0	0	1	5.7	10.2	2.6	6.3	997.9	0.4	1	0	7.0	5.5	5.7	18.6	270.7	0
2022-04-10	100	04:21:35	17:56:08	Sun	1	0	0	0	1	5.1	8.9	2.6	6.3	1009.4	0.9	0	0	4.2	5.7	5.2	13.7	277.3	0
2022-04-11	101	04:19:18	17:57:52	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	7.1	12.7	1.9	5.7	1013.4	0.0	0	0	10.7	2.7	3.3	10.0	276.5	0
2022-04-12	102	04:17:02	17:59:37	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	9.9	16.5	1.3	5.7	1012.7	0.0	0	0	12.3	5.3	3.2	8.7	115.5	0
2022-04-13	103	04:14:46	18:01:22	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	14.2	21.7	6.1	7.2	1011.7	0.0	0	0	9.4	6.5	3.0	7.4	132.2	0
2022-04-14	104	04:12:32	18:03:06	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	12.5	16.8	8.1	11.3	1013.3	4.2	0	0	4.0	7.2	2.6	7.9	303.6	0
2022-04-15	105	04:10:18	18:04:51	Fri	0	1	1	0	0	7.9	10.8	2.8	9.2	1018.8	0.4	0	0	0.0	7.3	5.4	11.1	329.8	0
2022-04-16	106	04:08:04	18:06:36	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	6.6	12.7	1.7	5.5	1027.8	0.0	0	0	11.1	3.3	4.5	10.9	26.7	0
2022-04-17	107	04:05:52	18:08:21	Sun	1	1	1	0	0	8.4	15.1	0.7	5.7	1023.6	0.0	0	0	13.3	2.9	2.8	8.0	14.7	0
2022-04-18	108	04:03:40	18:10:06	Mon	0	1	1	0	0	9.2	15.5	2.4	6.2	1014.3	0.0	0	0	12.5	4.5	2.9	8.5	30.6	0
2022-04-19	109	04:01:29	18:11:51	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	8.7	13.5	3.1	6.2	1009.9	0.0	0	0	9.6	4.0	4.6	11.9	31.4	0
2022-04-20	110	03:59:19	18:13:36	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	9.5	14.2	5.6	7.7	1010.1	0.2	0	0	3.1	6.8	4.0	11.1	3.4	0
2022-04-21	111	03:57:10	18:15:21	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	9.5	12.0	6.9	9.5	1007.9	0.1	0	0	0.0	7.5	2.8	7.3	38.9	0
2022-04-22	112	03:55:02	18:17:06	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	9.5	13.7	4.7	8.9	1005.1	0.0	0	0	1.1	5.7	4.1	11.3	70.2	0
2022-04-23	113	03:52:55	18:18:51	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	11.5	17.6	4.4	7.5	1004.3	0.0	0	0	11.5	1.4	4.7	10.4	68.5	0
2022-04-24	114	03:50:49	18:20:36	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	11.1	17.2	4.8	8.2	999.5	0.3	0	0	8.0	4.3	5.2	11.6	45.2	0
2022-04-25	115	03:48:45	18:22:20	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	8.8	13.7	5.1	8.3	1005.6	0.0	0	0	7.6	6.2	4.0	9.3	23.6	0
2022-04-26	116	03:46:41	18:24:05	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	11.5	17.4	3.7	7.2	1011.1	0.0	0	0	10.5	4.7	2.3	7.7	41.3	0
2022-04-27	117	03:44:38	18:25:50	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	12.1	17.9	6.2	7.2	1017.7	0.0	0	0	9.3	2.7	3.1	9.9	346.2	0
2022-04-28	118	03:42:37	18:27:34	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	11.5	17.6	4.9	7.7	1022.2	0.0	0	0	8.4	2.8	2.4	11.1	318.5	0
2022-04-29	119	03:40:37	18:29:19	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	12.9	19.2	5.3	7.2	1021.5	0.0	0	0	12.0	5.3	1.4	6.5	70.9	0
2022-04-30	120	03:38:38	18:31:03	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	13.1	19.8	7.2	7.9	1017.0	0.0	0	0	6.2	5.8	2.0	7.0	21.1	0
2022-05-01	121	03:36:41	18:32:46	Sun	1	1	0	0	0	11.7	15.4	6.2	8.1	1016.4	0.0	0	0	5.1	6.0	3.2	6.9	13.2	0
2022-05-02	122	03:34:45	18:34:30	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	13.4	19.5	6.6	8.3	1013.2	0.0	0	0	11.9	2.9	2.1	8.1	343.8	0
2022-05-03	123	03:32:51	18:36:13	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	13.0	18.4	7.7	8.4	1011.1	0.0	0	0	9.4	4.9	2.5	8.0	347.6	0
2022-05-04	124	03:30:57	18:37:56	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	14.2	19.4	6.5	9.8	1011.8	0.6	0	0	3.5	5.6	1.5	4.8	68.6	0
2022-05-05	125	03:29:06	18:39:39	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	14.3	18.9	9.4	10.1	1014.3	0.0	0	0	8.9	5.1	3.1	7.6	340.7	0
2022-05-06	126	03:27:16	18:41:21	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	14.4	20.0	6.5	9.5	1018.2	0.0	0	0	8.6	4.0	1.6	6.1	320.2	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-05-07	127	03:25:27	18:43:03	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	17.0	22.7	10.2	10.6	1016.2	1.0	0	0	10.9	5.1	3.0	10.4	301.4	0
2022-05-08	128	03:23:41	18:44:44	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	14.9	19.7	8.5	8.8	1019.6	0.0	0	0	12.7	3.1	3.5	9.1	349.0	0
2022-05-09	129	03:21:55	18:46:24	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	14.6	21.3	6.4	8.6	1021.5	0.0	0	0	14.6	1.3	2.7	7.1	82.6	0
2022-05-10	130	03:20:12	18:48:04	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	19.7	26.9	10.0	9.8	1012.8	0.0	0	0	10.7	5.8	2.9	9.4	185.1	0
2022-05-11	131	03:18:30	18:49:43	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	21.7	28.9	15.7	14.1	1004.6	3.3	1	0	6.7	6.4	4.0	16.3	227.2	0
2022-05-12	132	03:16:51	18:51:22	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	16.6	20.4	13.2	10.8	1008.7	0.0	0	0	8.2	5.4	4.8	15.5	268.8	0
2022-05-13	133	03:15:13	18:53:00	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	15.2	19.1	9.6	9.5	1011.2	0.0	0	0	6.7	5.2	4.0	12.5	265.9	0
2022-05-14	134	03:13:37	18:54:37	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	15.7	20.7	10.9	10.3	1013.3	0.0	0	0	7.9	4.5	4.6	11.5	290.3	0
2022-05-15	135	03:12:03	18:56:13	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	15.4	22.1	7.9	9.3	1015.7	0.0	0	0	14.7	1.6	2.1	6.1	12.2	0
2022-05-16	136	03:10:31	18:57:48	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	18.6	26.0	9.9	9.9	1012.7	5.8	0	0	12.7	5.8	3.8	8.1	87.7	0
2022-05-17	137	03:09:01	18:59:22	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	17.3	22.0	12.9	13.5	1014.4	0.6	0	0	2.7	6.7	2.2	6.9	329.4	0
2022-05-18	138	03:07:33	19:00:55	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	18.5	24.6	11.1	10.1	1019.1	0.0	0	0	13.5	4.3	3.9	8.7	128.9	0
2022-05-19	139	03:06:08	19:02:27	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	22.3	28.7	14.5	12.3	1014.3	0.0	0	0	12.6	6.0	3.1	8.0	183.8	0
2022-05-20	140	03:04:45	19:03:57	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	20.5	25.9	16.7	15.2	1010.6	9.7	1	0	8.9	6.8	3.6	16.9	272.1	0
2022-05-21	141	03:03:23	19:05:27	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	15.6	19.1	11.9	11.4	1009.9	1.7	0	0	7.7	4.3	7.3	17.4	281.2	0
2022-05-22	142	03:02:05	19:06:55	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	14.6	19.5	10.2	10.3	1010.2	0.0	0	0	10.1	4.2	3.4	7.5	300.2	0
2022-05-23	143	03:00:48	19:08:21	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	17.7	23.0	9.9	10.7	1002.7	1.8	0	0	11.6	5.8	4.3	10.8	124.1	0
2022-05-24	144	02:59:35	19:09:46	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	17.6	23.0	11.8	12.8	999.6	0.1	0	0	4.7	5.3	3.6	13.0	246.4	0
2022-05-25	145	02:58:23	19:11:10	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	16.1	20.9	9.6	10.7	1008.2	0.0	0	0	8.5	5.4	2.7	10.0	233.3	0
2022-05-26	146	02:57:14	19:12:31	Thu	0	1	0	0	0	17.2	21.3	13.9	11.0	1010.5	1.5	0	0	4.3	6.8	5.3	14.8	266.1	0
2022-05-27	147	02:56:08	19:13:51	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	14.0	18.5	8.5	11.0	1008.4	2.3	0	0	6.7	5.9	6.5	17.2	283.7	0
2022-05-28	148	02:55:04	19:15:10	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	11.4	16.3	8.6	9.3	1007.2	0.2	0	0	5.3	5.5	6.9	17.8	279.5	0
2022-05-29	149	02:54:03	19:16:26	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	12.0	15.2	9.6	9.8	1005.7	0.3	0	0	2.1	7.0	2.9	8.1	257.9	0
2022-05-30	150	02:53:05	19:17:40	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	12.2	17.5	7.9	9.7	1006.6	0.0	0	0	3.0	6.4	3.4	10.3	283.1	0
2022-05-31	151	02:52:10	19:18:53	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	14.9	21.0	7.9	9.5	1008.7	2.1	0	0	9.7	6.3	1.9	7.3	200.5	0
2022-06-01	152	02:51:17	19:20:03	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	15.2	20.1	11.9	11.1	1007.6	3.6	1	0	8.9	5.9	3.3	12.6	263.0	0
2022-06-02	153	02:50:27	19:21:11	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	14.6	19.7	10.0	9.8	1014.3	0.0	0	0	10.3	4.0	3.5	10.7	277.0	0
2022-06-03	154	02:49:40	19:22:17	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	18.6	25.9	7.9	10.3	1014.4	0.0	0	0	13.7	3.0	2.2	7.8	78.3	0
2022-06-04	155	02:48:56	19:23:20	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	19.0	24.6	12.2	11.4	1013.9	0.0	0	0	5.9	5.5	3.8	8.2	34.3	0
2022-06-05	156	02:48:15	19:24:21	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	20.7	28.4	10.1	12.1	1012.0	4.5	0	0	14.1	3.9	3.2	9.3	94.9	0
2022-06-06	157	02:47:37	19:25:20	Mon	0	1	0	0	0	20.1	25.9	14.7	16.0	1008.1	1.7	0	0	6.1	5.4	2.6	13.9	248.1	0
2022-06-07	158	02:47:02	19:26:16	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	19.2	24.9	13.1	12.3	1006.8	0.0	0	0	9.3	4.2	2.3	8.2	243.3	0
2022-06-08	159	02:46:31	19:27:09	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	20.6	26.4	14.2	13.6	1002.8	0.0	0	0	7.1	5.8	2.0	8.2	197.8	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T _{mean} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T _{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS _{mean} (m/s)	WS _{max} (m/s)	WD _{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-06-09	160	02:46:02	19:28:00	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	18.6	21.6	15.7	14.5	1005.9	0.2	0	0	2.3	6.4	3.0	7.6	288.5	0
2022-06-10	161	02:45:36	19:28:48	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	19.8	25.9	12.8	11.5	1015.5	0.0	0	0	14.7	2.1	3.7	10.7	296.1	0
2022-06-11	162	02:45:14	19:29:33	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	22.4	27.4	16.5	12.8	1015.4	0.7	0	0	6.1	5.6	2.9	10.3	251.9	0
2022-06-12	163	02:44:55	19:30:16	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	21.0	27.0	15.3	13.1	1013.5	0.0	0	0	9.6	5.3	2.9	9.6	314.1	0
2022-06-13	164	02:44:39	19:30:55	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	16.9	21.8	12.2	10.5	1012.4	0.0	0	0	9.2	5.3	5.1	15.1	303.9	0
2022-06-14	165	02:44:26	19:31:32	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	15.2	20.8	10.5	9.7	1016.0	0.0	0	0	11.3	5.2	3.9	13.5	300.5	0
2022-06-15	166	02:44:16	19:32:06	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	18.7	26.3	8.7	10.5	1013.6	0.0	0	0	14.9	3.3	2.0	6.5	65.4	0
2022-06-16	167	02:44:10	19:32:36	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	19.2	25.1	13.0	11.3	1013.1	0.0	0	0	12.5	5.3	4.0	10.3	347.1	0
2022-06-17	168	02:44:06	19:33:04	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	20.8	26.7	13.2	10.9	1017.1	0.0	0	0	11.5	6.0	2.6	8.4	292.8	0
2022-06-18	169	02:44:06	19:33:28	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	26.9	34.6	17.7	14.0	1009.6	0.0	0	0	14.0	2.3	3.6	10.7	262.3	1
2022-06-19	170	02:44:10	19:33:49	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	25.1	37.1	14.7	16.0	1002.7	2.9	1	0	10.2	3.0	5.2	14.2	319.7	1
2022-06-20	171	02:44:16	19:34:07	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	14.5	18.2	11.5	13.3	1006.0	6.8	1	0	2.6	6.5	3.3	11.8	294.4	0
2022-06-21	172	02:44:26	19:34:22	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	18.1	25.0	10.7	11.1	1007.8	0.0	0	0	12.3	2.5	3.8	9.7	287.5	0
2022-06-22	173	02:44:38	19:34:34	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	21.3	28.3	11.7	10.9	1006.8	0.0	0	0	16.0	1.2	2.2	7.4	338.0	0
2022-06-23	174	02:44:54	19:34:42	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	23.6	30.5	14.0	12.6	1008.3	0.0	0	0	16.1	0.6	3.0	8.5	69.0	0
2022-06-24	175	02:45:13	19:34:47	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	25.4	33.3	18.5	14.2	1003.6	0.0	0	0	11.3	3.6	3.7	11.5	137.7	0
2022-06-25	176	02:45:35	19:34:49	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	23.9	30.3	19.0	19.8	1005.6	0.0	1	0	5.1	6.0	1.8	6.5	89.4	0
2022-06-26	177	02:46:01	19:34:48	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	26.3	32.6	18.5	18.6	1008.3	0.0	0	0	10.1	3.3	2.0	7.4	138.7	1
2022-06-27	178	02:46:29	19:34:43	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	28.1	35.6	20.4	17.8	1007.7	1.6	1	0	12.0	4.3	4.0	14.5	206.8	1
2022-06-28	179	02:47:00	19:34:35	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	21.4	26.9	17.0	15.4	1014.2	0.0	0	0	8.9	5.2	3.8	10.9	326.4	0
2022-06-29	180	02:47:34	19:34:24	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	21.4	25.3	16.4	13.7	1011.5	0.0	0	0	7.5	6.8	3.9	7.8	81.4	0
2022-06-30	181	02:48:11	19:34:09	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	23.3	28.1	18.9	18.1	1006.9	0.0	0	0	10.4	5.3	2.8	6.6	70.4	0
2022-07-01	182	02:48:51	19:33:51	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	19.5	26.9	15.1	18.1	1009.5	1.2	0	0	3.9	6.1	4.4	13.9	279.5	0
2022-07-02	183	02:49:34	19:33:30	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	20.8	27.2	13.0	12.0	1016.8	0.0	0	0	15.3	1.3	2.2	7.6	189.9	0
2022-07-03	184	02:50:19	19:33:06	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	24.3	30.3	15.8	12.5	1011.6	0.3	0	0	14.8	1.8	2.9	10.7	141.8	0
2022-07-04	185	02:51:07	19:32:39	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	21.2	25.6	15.6	13.1	1012.0	0.0	0	0	12.9	2.8	3.9	9.8	302.5	0
2022-07-05	186	02:51:58	19:32:08	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	20.5	26.0	14.4	11.2	1014.1	0.1	0	0	13.1	2.9	3.3	9.5	318.2	0
2022-07-06	187	02:52:51	19:31:35	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	17.8	20.8	14.7	10.6	1015.3	3.1	0	0	6.3	6.3	4.6	11.0	291.2	0
2022-07-07	188	02:53:47	19:30:58	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	15.6	20.6	12.7	15.0	1011.7	6.9	0	0	1.3	7.3	3.7	13.9	254.7	0
2022-07-08	189	02:54:45	19:30:18	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	17.1	20.9	14.4	13.3	1019.2	0.0	0	0	3.3	5.9	4.9	11.3	289.7	0
2022-07-09	190	02:55:46	19:29:35	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	16.4	20.7	12.5	13.4	1016.4	6.3	0	0	2.7	6.3	4.3	11.5	291.8	0
2022-07-10	191	02:56:48	19:28:49	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	16.1	20.5	13.0	10.5	1013.6	0.0	0	0	4.6	6.1	5.3	11.6	300.3	0
2022-07-11	192	02:57:53	19:28:00	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	17.9	23.8	11.7	11.5	1014.9	0.0	0	0	14.1	3.3	3.8	8.9	310.4	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-07-12	193	02:59:00	19:27:09	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	20.8	27.5	12.2	11.8	1016.5	0.0	0	0	14.2	1.8	3.5	11.7	311.5	0
2022-07-13	194	03:00:10	19:26:14	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	24.1	30.9	16.8	14.0	1012.1	0.0	0	0	6.0	6.4	3.4	12.1	274.6	0
2022-07-14	195	03:01:21	19:25:17	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	19.6	25.0	14.7	11.1	1011.2	0.0	0	0	12.1	3.5	4.8	11.5	313.8	0
2022-07-15	196	03:02:34	19:24:17	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	16.8	21.2	12.2	10.4	1013.3	0.0	0	0	6.2	5.7	4.9	12.4	278.7	0
2022-07-16	197	03:03:49	19:23:14	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	17.9	22.3	13.8	10.6	1013.6	1.4	0	0	8.6	4.1	5.7	13.7	291.3	0
2022-07-17	198	03:05:05	19:22:08	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	17.7	24.1	11.1	10.5	1020.1	0.0	0	0	12.9	3.2	3.3	8.9	287.3	0
2022-07-18	199	03:06:24	19:21:00	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	22.9	29.2	14.0	11.8	1017.7	0.0	0	0	13.1	5.5	1.7	7.5	239.7	0
2022-07-19	200	03:07:44	19:19:49	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	27.1	35.8	15.4	11.8	1013.7	0.0	0	0	14.8	1.5	1.9	6.1	74.0	1
2022-07-20	201	03:09:05	19:18:36	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	30.0	37.9	19.3	13.4	1011.7	0.0	0	0	14.6	2.1	2.6	8.8	119.9	1
2022-07-21	202	03:10:28	19:17:20	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	24.8	29.7	20.0	17.3	1010.9	1.7	1	0	7.9	4.6	3.2	8.9	225.2	1
2022-07-22	203	03:11:53	19:16:02	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	21.2	25.5	17.4	17.4	1012.2	1.9	0	0	7.0	5.6	3.4	8.7	281.5	0
2022-07-23	204	03:13:18	19:14:41	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	18.9	24.8	14.6	13.7	1012.0	1.5	0	0	8.7	4.0	3.1	9.1	310.7	0
2022-07-24	205	03:14:45	19:13:18	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	21.5	28.7	12.8	11.9	1013.5	0.0	0	0	15.5	3.0	2.2	6.8	247.5	0
2022-07-25	206	03:16:14	19:11:53	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	26.0	35.7	18.0	15.4	1004.6	6.5	1	0	11.2	4.7	3.8	14.7	182.4	1
2022-07-26	207	03:17:43	19:10:26	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	19.8	24.5	16.3	16.0	1007.2	2.1	0	0	7.2	5.8	4.1	13.7	284.9	0
2022-07-27	208	03:19:13	19:08:56	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	17.1	21.5	12.6	10.4	1011.9	0.0	0	0	7.0	4.8	3.9	9.2	295.0	0
2022-07-28	209	03:20:45	19:07:25	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	18.1	24.1	10.5	10.7	1013.9	0.0	0	0	13.9	3.9	1.9	6.9	2.6	0
2022-07-29	210	03:22:17	19:05:51	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	22.0	28.9	14.7	11.6	1011.8	0.0	0	0	10.7	5.5	4.0	9.6	79.3	0
2022-07-30	211	03:23:50	19:04:15	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	21.8	26.9	16.6	12.4	1010.8	0.0	0	0	11.0	4.8	2.8	8.4	74.1	0
2022-07-31	212	03:25:24	19:02:37	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	22.9	29.0	13.8	13.9	1009.1	0.0	0	0	11.0	3.9	2.1	9.6	292.8	0
2022-08-01	213	03:26:59	19:00:58	Mon	0	0	1	0	1	21.3	25.4	17.5	17.1	1008.9	0.0	0	0	2.7	6.8	4.0	9.7	304.3	0
2022-08-02	214	03:28:34	18:59:16	Tue	0	0	1	0	1	22.5	28.4	16.5	13.1	1012.2	0.0	0	0	11.1	5.6	1.9	7.7	262.1	0
2022-08-03	215	03:30:10	18:57:33	Wed	0	0	1	0	1	27.0	34.4	19.1	13.4	1010.1	0.0	0	0	13.8	4.1	1.6	6.1	188.4	1
2022-08-04	216	03:31:46	18:55:48	Thu	0	0	1	0	1	29.7	37.3	18.9	14.6	1007.5	0.0	0	0	14.2	3.3	2.2	10.7	166.8	1
2022-08-05	217	03:33:24	18:54:01	Fri	0	0	1	0	1	23.2	29.1	16.0	17.4	1008.7	0.4	0	0	3.9	5.7	4.4	12.3	319.0	0
2022-08-06	218	03:35:01	18:52:13	Sat	1	0	1	0	1	18.0	23.8	13.2	10.3	1019.1	0.0	0	0	11.1	2.8	4.0	11.4	319.1	0
2022-08-07	219	03:36:39	18:50:23	Sun	1	0	1	0	1	19.0	25.5	11.5	9.5	1019.1	0.0	0	0	12.9	1.7	1.6	6.0	43.8	0
2022-08-08	220	03:38:18	18:48:31	Mon	0	0	1	0	1	21.2	28.3	13.1	10.1	1018.6	0.0	0	0	10.8	2.3	2.3	7.6	31.8	0
2022-08-09	221	03:39:56	18:46:38	Tue	0	0	1	0	1	22.3	28.2	16.6	12.1	1021.1	0.0	0	0	11.6	4.8	3.6	8.0	25.4	0
2022-08-10	222	03:41:35	18:44:43	Wed	0	0	1	0	1	22.2	29.1	14.3	11.8	1020.7	0.0	0	0	14.2	2.2	2.5	7.4	29.3	0
2022-08-11	223	03:43:15	18:42:47	Thu	0	0	1	0	1	23.6	30.1	14.9	11.0	1017.6	0.0	0	0	14.1	1.7	2.7	7.4	77.4	0
2022-08-12	224	03:44:54	18:40:49	Fri	0	0	1	0	1	23.9	30.2	15.5	12.0	1015.6	0.0	0	0	13.3	2.0	2.8	10.6	88.5	0
2022-08-13	225	03:46:34	18:38:50	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	24.0	29.4	18.6	16.2	1012.1	0.2	0	0	3.5	5.9	2.3	9.7	76.4	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-08-14	226	03:48:14	18:36:50	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	26.3	32.4	20.2	16.6	1005.3	0.0	0	0	12.7	5.5	2.7	10.0	81.1	1
2022-08-15	227	03:49:54	18:34:49	Mon	0	0	1	0	0	23.8	31.7	19.3	19.7	999.7	20.4	1	0	7.4	3.9	3.0	13.8	122.0	1
2022-08-16	228	03:51:35	18:32:46	Tue	0	0	1	0	0	24.0	30.3	18.1	18.5	1003.1	0.0	0	0	11.7	1.6	1.6	6.9	228.3	1
2022-08-17	229	03:53:15	18:30:42	Wed	0	0	1	0	0	26.3	32.3	18.1	16.3	1005.4	0.0	0	0	10.9	5.0	1.7	5.4	72.7	1
2022-08-18	230	03:54:55	18:28:37	Thu	0	0	1	0	0	25.7	34.4	20.1	18.3	1004.4	12.9	1	0	6.4	6.8	2.6	15.3	30.0	1
2022-08-19	231	03:56:36	18:26:30	Fri	0	0	1	0	0	21.7	24.0	19.9	22.0	1004.7	0.8	1	0	1.0	7.8	4.2	8.8	318.9	0
2022-08-20	232	03:58:16	18:24:23	Sat	1	0	1	0	0	20.2	22.1	19.3	20.3	1008.4	1.0	0	0	0.0	7.8	3.1	7.2	313.6	0
2022-08-21	233	03:59:57	18:22:15	Sun	1	0	1	0	0	19.8	25.3	15.3	14.6	1009.9	0.0	0	0	7.9	5.8	3.1	7.9	330.4	0
2022-08-22	234	04:01:37	18:20:05	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	19.6	24.4	13.7	14.4	1011.4	0.0	0	0	5.1	6.2	2.3	7.9	67.3	0
2022-08-23	235	04:03:18	18:17:55	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	20.9	25.9	17.5	16.7	1012.8	0.0	0	0	4.7	4.9	3.3	8.4	30.4	0
2022-08-24	236	04:04:58	18:15:44	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	21.5	27.5	16.3	19.4	1015.0	0.0	0	0	7.7	2.4	2.2	6.6	39.7	0
2022-08-25	237	04:06:38	18:13:31	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	22.5	28.2	17.3	20.6	1013.0	0.0	0	0	7.5	2.7	2.9	9.0	54.2	1
2022-08-26	238	04:08:19	18:11:18	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	22.0	29.2	19.1	21.4	1007.6	17.4	1	0	5.2	5.3	2.5	11.2	13.4	1
2022-08-27	239	04:09:59	18:09:04	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	20.5	24.2	18.2	21.3	1006.5	5.4	0	0	1.0	7.6	3.8	10.0	328.5	0
2022-08-28	240	04:11:39	18:06:50	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	17.7	21.8	14.8	16.0	1010.6	0.0	0	0	5.7	4.8	4.2	8.0	304.9	0
2022-08-29	241	04:13:19	18:04:34	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	16.8	23.5	12.9	-999	-999.0	0.0	0	0	4.7	4.5	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0
2022-08-30	242	04:14:59	18:02:18	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	17.5	23.0	13.2	-999	-999.0	0.0	0	0	6.0	5.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0
2022-08-31	243	04:16:39	18:00:01	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	17.9	22.9	13.5	-999	-999.0	0.0	0	0	9.9	5.2	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0
2022-09-01	244	04:18:19	17:57:43	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	17.1	23.0	13.0	-999	-999.0	0.0	0	0	10.6	2.8	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0
2022-09-02	245	04:19:59	17:55:25	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	17.0	22.1	11.5	-999	-999.0	0.0	0	0	7.1	3.5	-999.0	11.4	-999.0	0
2022-09-03	246	04:21:38	17:53:06	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	16.7	22.5	10.7	9.9	1012.9	0.0	0	0	6.5	4.1	4.1	10.2	90.6	0
2022-09-04	247	04:23:18	17:50:47	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	18.3	24.5	12.8	10.8	1016.1	0.0	0	0	12.4	4.4	4.1	9.8	88.6	0
2022-09-05	248	04:24:58	17:48:27	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	18.5	24.1	13.2	11.9	1018.6	0.0	0	0	12.4	4.7	4.5	9.9	89.8	0
2022-09-06	249	04:26:37	17:46:07	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	18.1	22.6	13.2	10.9	1014.5	0.0	0	0	7.5	6.0	4.5	10.2	93.5	0
2022-09-07	250	04:28:16	17:43:46	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	19.5	25.7	13.6	13.8	1008.6	0.0	1	0	6.8	4.8	3.4	9.5	98.7	0
2022-09-08	251	04:29:56	17:41:25	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	16.5	18.0	14.8	14.9	1003.8	13.2	1	0	0.0	6.6	3.0	7.6	110.9	0
2022-09-09	252	04:31:35	17:39:03	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	17.6	23.1	13.4	15.0	1005.6	0.0	1	0	8.1	4.3	2.2	7.5	174.2	0
2022-09-10	253	04:33:14	17:36:41	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	16.9	21.9	12.5	14.4	1006.3	0.9	1	0	10.4	4.1	2.1	7.3	248.6	0
2022-09-11	254	04:34:54	17:34:19	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	15.7	19.7	12.9	14.9	1010.2	0.0	0	0	1.9	5.9	3.0	8.0	323.0	0
2022-09-12	255	04:36:33	17:31:56	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	15.5	21.0	11.0	-999	1010.7	0.0	0	0	8.4	3.7	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0
2022-09-13	256	04:38:12	17:29:33	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	15.3	20.3	13.8	-999	1003.0	1.5	0	0	3.5	5.5	-999.0	7.7	-999.0	0
2022-09-14	257	04:39:51	17:27:10	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	15.2	18.9	12.0	-999	999.5	0.0	0	0	3.6	7.0	-999.0	6.1	-999.0	0
2022-09-15	258	04:41:30	17:24:47	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	14.5	18.6	11.9	12.7	997.9	0.1	0	0	5.1	5.4	4.3	12.2	269.4	0

Date	DOY	Sunrise (UTC)	Sunset (UTC)	DOW	Week-end	Public holiday	School holiday	Other event	IOP	T_{mean} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	VP (hPa)	P (hPa)	PRCP (mm)	Thunders. (No.)	SH (cm)	Sun (h)	CCF (okta)	WS_{mean} (m/s)	WS_{max} (m/s)	WD_{mean} (°)	Heat warning
2022-09-16	259	04:43:10	17:22:23	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	13.6	18.3	10.5	10.5	998.3	3.2	0	0	6.6	4.4	5.6	13.8	258.9	0
2022-09-17	260	04:44:49	17:20:00	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	12.4	16.5	10.0	11.4	998.9	2.4	0	0	4.7	7.0	5.6	15.6	273.2	0
2022-09-18	261	04:46:28	17:17:36	Sun	1	0	0	0	0	10.9	14.7	8.8	10.5	1000.8	4.9	0	0	6.9	6.1	5.4	14.1	277.8	0
2022-09-19	262	04:48:08	17:15:12	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	10.8	16.1	8.5	11.4	1006.1	10.0	1	0	1.2	6.3	4.3	11.8	289.2	0
2022-09-20	263	04:49:47	17:12:48	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	10.5	15.1	7.0	10.9	1013.9	5.5	1	0	7.2	3.9	3.5	17.3	289.6	0
2022-09-21	264	04:51:27	17:10:24	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	11.1	16.6	6.2	10.4	1019.4	0.0	0	0	6.9	3.2	2.3	7.6	307.1	0
2022-09-22	265	04:53:07	17:08:01	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	11.1	16.7	5.4	9.4	1018.4	0.0	0	0	7.4	2.3	1.3	6.1	116.2	0
2022-09-23	266	04:54:47	17:05:37	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	11.4	17.6	3.9	9.2	1012.8	0.0	0	0	10.2	4.4	1.7	5.8	140.3	0
2022-09-24	267	04:56:27	17:03:13	Sat	1	0	0	0	0	12.6	16.5	9.1	11.2	1007.8	0.0	0	0	0.3	6.9	2.0	4.9	75.5	0
2022-09-25	268	04:58:07	17:00:50	Sun	1	0	0	Marathon	0	14.3	19.5	10.9	11.8	1005.4	0.0	0	0	5.1	6.7	2.4	6.6	279.7	0
2022-09-26	269	04:59:47	16:58:26	Mon	0	0	0	0	0	13.6	17.3	10.8	10.6	997.8	0.7	0	0	5.4	6.8	3.2	10.0	207.5	0
2022-09-27	270	05:01:28	16:56:03	Tue	0	0	0	0	0	11.2	13.7	7.9	11.3	989.8	5.0	0	0	1.0	6.7	3.0	11.7	205.5	0
2022-09-28	271	05:03:09	16:53:40	Wed	0	0	0	0	0	9.4	12.3	7.1	9.8	991.4	0.0	0	0	5.0	6.4	2.3	7.0	213.0	0
2022-09-29	272	05:04:50	16:51:18	Thu	0	0	0	0	0	9.6	14.7	5.2	9.7	997.8	0.0	0	0	3.6	5.3	1.9	5.6	185.7	0
2022-09-30	273	05:06:31	16:48:55	Fri	0	0	0	0	0	10.7	17.5	3.2	9.4	1005.1	0.0	0	0	9.3	1.2	1.8	7.7	177.3	0

Table A.2: Conditions for colour codes per variable used in Table A.1.

Variable	Condition	Colour	Description	Reference
Weekend, Public holiday, School holiday, Other event, IOP	True (1 or other entry)			
T_{max}	< 0 °C		Icing day	https://www.climdex.org/learn/indices/#index-ID
	≥ 25 °C		Summer day	https://www.climdex.org/learn/indices/#index-SU
	≥ 30 °C		Hot day	https://www.dwd.de/DE/service/lexikon/Functions/glossar.html?lv2=101094&lv3=101162
T_{min}	< 0 °C		Frost day	https://www.climdex.org/learn/indices/#index-FD
	≥ 20 °C		Tropical night	https://www.climdex.org/learn/indices/#index-TR
PRCP	≥ 0.1 mm		Rainy day	https://www.dwd.de/DE/service/lexikon/Functions/glossar.html?lv2=102134&lv3=102196
	≥ 5 mm			
	≥ 10 mm			https://www.climdex.org/learn/indices/#index-R10mm
	≥ 20 mm			https://www.climdex.org/learn/indices/#index-R20mm
Thunders.	≥ 1		Thunderstorm day	https://www.dwd.de/DE/service/lexikon/Functions/glossar.html?lv2=100932&lv3=101024
CCF	> 6.4 okta		Cloudy day	https://www.dwd.de/DE/service/lexikon/Functions/glossar.html?lv2=102672&lv3=102822
WS_{max}	≥ 17.2 m s ⁻¹		Storm day	https://www.dwd.de/DE/service/lexikon/Functions/glossar.html?lv2=102248&lv3=102642
Heat warning	1 or 3			https://opendata.dwd.de/climate_environment/health/historical_alerts/heat_warnings/Description_historical_heat_alerts.pdf

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https://opendata.dwd.de/climate_environment/CDC/observations_germany/climate/monthly/kl/historical/

DWD 2023a: Historical daily station observations (temperature, pressure, precipitation, sunshine duration, etc.) for Germany, Version v23.3.

https://opendata.dwd.de/climate_environment/CDC/observations_germany/climate/daily/kl/historical/

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